

**BATCH SORPTION EXPERIMENTS ON RECYCLING
BUILDING WASTES AND DEWATERED ALUM
SLUDGE AS REACTIVE PACKING MEDIA IN
PERMEABLE REACTIVE BARRIERS (PRBs) TO
TREAT THE HEAVY METALS OF THE GROUND
WATER CONTAMINATED BY LANDFILL-
LEACHATE**

Undergraduate research proposal report submitted in partial fulfilment of the degree
of Bachelor of the Science of Engineering

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PREFACE

This report consists the final documents related to the undergraduate research thesis “Batch sorption experiments on recycled building waste and dewatered alum sludge as reactive packing media in Permeable Reactive Barriers to treat the heavy metals of the ground water contaminated by landfill-leachate”, which is going to be preceded. The thesis mainly consists of four chapters namely introduction to the research, literature review, methodology and results and discussion. Brief outline of the content of each chapter is presented below.

The first chapter contains background, aim and objectives, scope of the study and significance of the study. This conveys a detailed description on the innovative leachate treatments mechanism and why this treatment mechanism is important over conventional treatment mechanisms.

The second chapter consists of the literature review, which explains the past studies related to the research. It mainly consists of leachate composition, leachate treatment, instruments used, isotherms used, etc.

Third chapter includes the methodology. It explains the planning steps, selection of reactive materials and the batch experiments conducted.

The fourth chapter describes the results and discussion. This includes the overall results of the batch experiments carried out and discussion for the above results. The conclusions and the future recommendations are described in the fifth chapter.

Finally reference list and appendix are included.

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ABSTRACT

The Batch sorption experiments were conducted in order to treat the heavy metals in the ground water which is contaminated by landfill – leachate. For this process some building waste materials and dewatered alum sludge (DAS) are used as for the treatment materials. For the accuracy of the works, the building waste materials are classified into four categories; Floor wastes (FW), Brick wastes (BW), Roof wastes (RW) and Concrete wastes (CW).

Here for the batch sorption experiments, contact time and adsorbent dosage were considered as the major parameters affecting the adsorption process. Therefore initially kinematic experiments (Time optimization) were conducted at different time intervals using a pre-determined mass value of adsorbent. Then by using the optimized time from the kinematic experiments for each selected reactive materials, adsorption isotherm (Mass optimization) experiments were conducted using a series of adsorbent dosage to obtain the optimum adsorption capacity of each materials.

In this research removal efficiencies of heavy metals like Fe, Cd, Zn, Mn, Cu, Pb and As for each selected reactive materials were analysed individually. Results show that Fe, Cd and Pb were highly removable heavy metals from the diluted leachate samples and RW has the lowest adsorbing capacity of heavy metals. Finally according to the adsorption isotherms, the theoretical adsorption capacities were obtained for the adsorption isotherm experiment samples.

Keywords: *Batch experiments, Adsorption, Isotherms, Heavy metals, Reactive media, Ground water*

CONTENTS

CHAPTER 1.....	1
INTRODUCTION TO THE RESEARCH.....	1
1.1 BACKGROUND.....	1
1.2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES	2
1.2.1 Aim.....	2
1.2.2 Objectives.....	3
1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY	3
1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY.....	3
CHAPTER 2.....	4
LITERATURE REVIEW.....	4
2.1 INTRODUCTION.....	4
2.2 PERMEABLE REACTIVE BARRIER (PRB).....	5
2.2.1 Definition of Permeable Reactive Barrier	5
2.2.2 PRB system configurations	6
2.2.3 Installation of PRB in field.....	8
2.2.4 Advantages and disadvantages of PRB	9
2.3 REACTIVE MEDIA	10
2.3.1 Reactive Medias used in past studies	10
2.4 EFFECT OF HEAVY METALS IN LEACHATE	14
2.4.1 Leachate composition.....	15
2.5 LANDFILL-LEACHATE TREATMENT.....	15
2.6 ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS	16
2.6.1 Adsorbate	16
2.6.2 Adsorbent	16
2.6.3 Freundlich Isotherm Model.....	16
2.6.4 Langmuir Isotherm Model	17
2.6.6 Elovich Isotherm Model.....	18
2.6.7 Dubinin – Radushkevich Isotherm Model	19
CHAPTER 3.....	20
METHODOLOGY	20
3.1 OVERALL PROCEDURE	20
3.2 CATEGORIZATION OF REACTIVE MATERIALS	21
3.3 MATERIAL PREPARATION.....	23
3.3.1 Reactive materials	23
3.3.2 Diluted Landfill Leachate.....	24

3.4 BATCH SORPTION EXPERIMENTS	26
3.4.1 Overall methodology of batch sorption experiments	26
3.4.2 A typical example for the batch sorption experiment procedure	26
3.4.3 Testing Parameters	28
3.4.5 Time optimization experiments (Kinematic experiments).....	30
3.4.6 Mass optimization experiments (Adsorption isotherm experiments)	32
3.5 ANALYSIS	34
3.5.1 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	34
3.5.2 Conductivity, pH and ORP analysis.....	35
3.5.3 Heavy metals	36
CHAPTER 4.....	42
RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	42
4.1 pH.....	42
4.1.1 Trial experiments.....	42
4.1.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments	43
4.2 CONDUCTIVITY	43
4.2.1 Trial Experiments	43
4.2.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments	44
4.3 OXIDATION REDUCTION POTENTIAL (ORP).....	45
4.3.1 Trial Experiments	45
4.3.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments	46
4.4 TOTAL DISSOLVED SOLIDS (TDS)	46
4.4.1 Kinematic experiments.....	46
4.4.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments	47
4.5 HEAVY METALS REMOVAL	48
4.5.1 Kinematic Experiments	48
4.5.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments	55
4.6 PLOTTING ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS	61
4.6.2 Theoretical adsorption capacities	68
4.7 EFFECT OF INITIAL PH.....	68
4.7.1 Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)	69
4.7.2 Floor waste (FW)	69
4.7.3 Brick waste (BW).....	70
4.7.4 Roof waste (RW).....	71
4.7.5 Concrete waste (CW)	71
CHAPTER 5.....	72

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	72
5.1 CONCLUSIONS.....	72
5.2 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS.....	73
REFERENCES.....	74
APPENDIX A.....	77
RESULTS OF pH VALUES.....	77
APPENDIX B.....	79
RESULTS OF CONDUCTIVITY VALUES.....	79
APPENDIX C.....	81
RESULTS OF ORP VALUES.....	81
APPENDIX D.....	83
RESULTS OF TDS ANALYSIS.....	83
APPENDIX E.....	88
HEAVY METALS REMOVAL OF KINEMATIC EXPERIMENTS.....	88
APPENDIX F.....	100
HEAVY METALS REMOVAL OF ADSORPTION ISOTHERM EXPERIMENTS.....	100
APPENDIX G.....	109
SUMMARY TABLES.....	109

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1: Table of Constituents of Municipal landfill-leachate	15
Table 3.1: Constituents of reactive materials	22
Table 3.2: pH and temperature values of leachate samples	25
Table 3.3: Wastewater parameters to be measured.....	28
Table 3.4: Weight of adsorbent considered for Trial 1	29
Table 3.5: Weight of adsorbent considered for Trial 2	32
Table 3.6: Time of stirring for DAS of kinematic experiment	32
Table 3.7: Time of stirring for other materials.....	32
Table 3.8: Weight of adsorbent considered for DAS mass optimization.....	33
Table 3.9: Weight of adsorbent considered for BW mass optimization	34
Table 3.10: Weight of adsorbent considered for RW mass optimization	34
Table 3.11: Instruments used for heavy metals analysis.....	36
Table 3.12: Absorbance values from spectrophotometer.....	39
Table 3.13: Standard solutions ranges for heavy metals.....	40
Table 4.1: The type of heavy metal best removed by different reactive materials at the optimum contact time (From kinematic experiments).....	54
Table 4.2: Best reactive material for different heavy metals at the optimum contact time	54
Table 4.3: Selected optimum time for each reactive material.....	54
Table 4.4: The type of heavy metal best removed by different reactive materials at the optimum masses	60
Table 4.5: The type of reactive materials best suited for the removal of different types of heavy metals at the optimum masses	61
Table 4.6: Optimum masses for different reactive materials	61
Table 4.12: Isotherm constants of DAS samples of Mass optimization	63
Table 4.13: Isotherm constants of FW samples of Mass optimization	64
Table 4.14: Isotherm constants of BW samples of Mass optimization.....	65
Table 4.15: Isotherm constants of RW samples of Mass optimization.....	67
Table 4.16: Isotherm constants of CW samples of Mass optimization.....	68
Table A.1: pH values of samples of 1 st Trial experiment	77
Table A.2: pH values of samples of 2 nd Trial experiment.....	77
Table A.3: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –DAS	77

Table A.4: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –FW	78
Table A.5: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –BW	78
Table A.6: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –RW	78
Table A.7: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –CW	78
Table B.1: Conductivity values of samples of 1 st Trial experiment.....	79
Table B.2: Conductivity values of samples of 2 nd Trial experiment.....	79
Table B.3: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – DAS	79
Table B.4: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – FW	80
Table B.5: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – BW	80
Table B.6: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – RW	80
Table B.7: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – CW	80
Table C.1: ORP values of samples of 1st Trial experiment.....	81
Table C.2: ORP values of samples of 2nd Trial experiment.....	81
Table C.3: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – DAS.....	81
Table C.4: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – FW	81
Table C.5: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – BW	82
Table C.6: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – RW	82
Table C.7: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – CW	82
Table D.1: TDS analysis for 1st Trial experiment	83
Table D.2: TDS analysis for 2nd Trial experiment.....	83
Table D.3: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – DAS.....	84
Table D.4: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – FW.....	84
Table D.5: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – BW	84
Table D.6: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – RW	85
Table D.7: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – CW	85
Table D.8: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – DAS	85
Table D.9: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – FW	86
Table D.10: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – BW	86
Table D.11: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – RW	86
Table D.12: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – CW	87
Table E.1: Fe removal by DAS of kinematic experiments	88
Table E.2: Cd removal by DAS of kinematic experiments.....	88

Table E.3: Zn removal by DAS of kinematic experiments	88
Table E.4: Mn removal by DAS of kinematic experiments.....	89
Table E.5: Cu removal by DAS of kinematic experiments.....	89
Table E.6: Pb removal by DAS of kinematic experiments	89
Table E.7: As removal by DAS of kinematic experiments	90
Table E.8: Fe removal by FW of kinematic experiments	90
Table E.9: Cd removal by FW of kinematic experiments.....	90
Table E.10: Zn removal by FW of kinematic experiments.....	91
Table E.11: Mn removal by FW of kinematic experiments.....	91
Table E.12: Cu removal by FW of kinematic experiments.....	91
Table E.13: Pb removal by FW of kinematic experiments	92
Table E.14: As removal by FW of kinematic experiments	92
Table E.15: Fe removal by BW of kinematic experiments.....	92
Table E.16: Cd removal by BW of kinematic experiments	93
Table E.17: Zn removal by BW of kinematic experiments	93
Table E.18: Mn removal by BW of kinematic experiments	93
Table E.19: Cu removal by BW of kinematic experiments	94
Table E.20: Pb removal by BW of kinematic experiments.....	94
Table E.21: As removal by BW of kinematic experiments	94
Table E.22: Fe removal by RW of kinematic experiments.....	95
Table E.23: Cd removal by RW of kinematic experiments	95
Table E.24: Zn removal by RW of kinematic experiments	95
Table E.25: Mn removal by RW of kinematic experiments	96
Table E.26: Cu removal by RW of kinematic experiments	96
Table E.27: Pb removal by RW of kinematic experiments.....	96
Table E.28: As removal by RW of kinematic experiments	97
Table E.29: Fe removal by CW of kinematic experiments.....	97
Table E.30: Cd removal by CW of kinematic experiments	97
Table E.31: Zn removal by CW of kinematic experiments	98
Table E.32: Mn removal by CW of kinematic experiments	98
Table E.33: Cu removal by CW of kinematic experiments	98
Table E.34: Pb removal by CW of kinematic experiments.....	99
Table E.35: As removal by CW of kinematic experiments	99
Table F.1: Fe removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments	100

Table F.2: Cd removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	100
Table F.3: Zn removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments	100
Table F.4: Mn removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	100
Table F.5: Cu removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	101
Table F.6: Pb removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments	101
Table F.7: As removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments	101
Table F.8: Fe removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments	101
Table F.9: Cd removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	102
Table F.10: Zn removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments	102
Table F.11: Mn removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	102
Table F.12: Cu removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	102
Table F.13: Pb removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments	103
Table F.14: As removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments	103
Table F.15: Fe removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments	103
Table F.16: Cd removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments	103
Table F.17: Zn removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	104
Table F.18: Mn removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments	104
Table F.19: Cu removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments	104
Table F.20: Pb removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	104
Table F.21: As removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	105
Table F.22: Fe removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments	105
Table F.23: Cd removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments	105
Table F.24: Zn removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments	105
Table F.25: Mn removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments	106
Table F.26: Cu removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments	106
Table F.27: Pb removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	106
Table F.28: As removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	106
Table F.29: Fe removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments	107
Table F.30: Cd removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments	107
Table F.31: Zn removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	107
Table F.32: Mn removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments	107
Table F.33: Cu removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments	108
Table F.34: Pb removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	108
Table F.35: As removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	108

Table G.1: Time optimization experiment results.....	109
Table G.2: Mass optimization experiment results.....	110

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram of the leachate production.....	4
Figure 2.2: Leachate formation	5
Figure 2.3: Leachate formed from Landfill.....	5
Figure 2.4: Schematic diagram of PRB.....	6
Figure 2.5: Continuous PRB	7
Figure 2.6: Funnel and gate system.....	7
Figure 2.7: Injection wall configuration	8
Figure 2.8: Passive collector	8
Figure 2.9: PRB installation at field.....	9
Figure 2.10: Isotherm variations (Al-Salihy, 2016).....	11
Figure 2.11: Optimization of time (BULUT Yasemin, 2007)	12
Figure 2.12: Isotherm analysis for heavy metals removal	13
Figure 2.13: Freundlich isotherm variation.....	16
Figure 2.14: Langmuir isotherm variation	17
Figure 2.15: Temkin isotherm variation.....	18
Figure 2.16: Elovich isotherm variation.....	18
Figure 2.17: Dubinin – Radushkevich isotherm variation	19
Figure 3.1: Overall procedure	20
Figure 3.2: Sludge drying bed, Water treatment plant, Hapugala.....	21
Figure 3.3: Sieve analysis test apparatus.....	23
Figure 3.4: Prepared reactive materials.....	24
Figure 3.5: Heenpandala landfill area	24
Figure 3.6: Instantaneous landfill leachate categories	25
Figure 3.7: Collection of Leachate.....	25
Figure 3.8: Obtaining optimum parameter.....	26
Figure 3.9: Membrane filter technique using vacuum pump	27
Figure 3.10: Bottling and labelling the supernatant samples	28
Figure 3.11: Trial experiment setup for typical waste material	29
Figure 3.12: Setup for 1st Trial experiment.....	29
Figure 3.13: Setup for 2nd Trial experiment.....	30
Figure 3.14: Kinematic experiment samples.....	31
Figure 3.15: Setup for kinematic experiment by DAS.....	31

Figure 3.16: Setup for DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments.....	33
Figure 3.17: Setup for BW of adsorption isotherm experiments	33
Figure 3.18: Setup for RW of adsorption isotherm experiments	34
Figure 3.19: Petri dishes with supernatant for TDS analysis	35
Figure 3.20: Measuring pH values (i) and measuring conductivity values (ii) of the supernatants.....	35
Figure 3.21: Conductivity meter (i), pH meter (ii) & ORP meter (iii).....	36
Figure 3.22: Samples preserved for heavy metal analysis	37
Figure 3.23: Standards prepared for Fe analysis.....	38
Figure 3.24: Spectrophotometer.....	38
Figure 3.25: Standard calibration curve for Fe analysis	39
Figure 3.26: Stock standards and micro-pipette.....	39
Figure 3.27: Standard curves obtained from AAS	40
Figure 3.28: Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer.....	41
Figure 4.1: pH variation for samples of Trial 1	42
Figure 4.2: pH variation for samples of Trial 2	42
Figure 4.3: pH variation for reactive materials of mass optimization	43
Figure 4.4: Conductivity variation for Trial 1.....	43
Figure 4.5: Conductivity variation for Trial 2.....	44
Figure 4.6: Conductivity variation for Mass optimization experiments	44
Figure 4.7: ORP variation for Trial 1.....	45
Figure 4.8: ORP variation for Trial 2.....	45
Figure 4.9: ORP variation for Mass optimization.....	46
Figure 4.10: TDS analysis for Time optimization	47
Figure 4.11: TDS analysis for Mass optimization	47
Figure 4.12: Fe analysis for Time optimization.....	48
Figure 4.13: Cd analysis for Time optimization	49
Figure 4.14: Zn analysis for Time optimization.....	50
Figure 4.15: Mn analysis for Time optimization	50
Figure 4.16: Cu analysis for Time optimization	51
Figure 4.17: Pb analysis for Time optimization.....	52
Figure 4.18: As analysis for Time optimization.....	52
Figure 4.19: Removal efficiency variation at the optimum contact time (From kinematic experiments).....	53

Figure 4.20: Fe analysis for Mass optimization	55
Figure 4.21: Cd analysis for Mass optimization	56
Figure 4.22: Zn analysis for Mass optimization.....	57
Figure 4.23: Mn analysis for Mass optimization	57
Figure 4.24: Cu analysis for Mass optimization	58
Figure 4.25: Pb analysis for Mass optimization.....	59
Figure 4.26: As analysis for Mass optimization.....	59
Figure 4.27: Variation of the best removal efficiencies at the optimum mass.....	60
Figure 4.33: Isotherm variations of DAS samples of Mass optimization	62
Figure 4.34: Isotherm variations of FW samples of Mass optimization	64
Figure 4.35: Isotherm variations of BW samples of Mass optimization	65
Figure 4.36: Isotherm variations of RW samples of Mass optimization	66
Figure 4.37: Isotherm variations of CW samples of Mass optimization	68
Figure 4.38: Effect of initial pH for DAS samples	69
Figure 4.39: Effect of initial pH for FW samples	70
Figure 4.40: Effect of initial pH for BW samples.....	70
Figure 4.41: Effect of initial pH for RW samples.....	71
Figure 4.42: Effect of initial pH for CW samples.....	71

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ORP	-	Oxidation Reduction Potential
DAS	-	Dewatered Alum Sludge
TDS	-	Total Dissolved Solids
PRB	-	Permeable Reactive Barrier
AAS	-	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometry

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION TO THE RESEARCH

1.1 BACKGROUND

On Earth, ground water reservoir is the largest freshwater reservoir, and it is considered as a natural high quality drinkable water source (Higgins & Monica, 2011). These ground water reservoirs get much polluted by the landfill-leachate, which is produced as a result of rain water passing through the landfill (Naidu & Ravi, 2013). Harmful effects result by these landfill-leachate after it contaminates the groundwater.

Proper management of solid waste is very important to all the countries. The proper waste management depends on “waste characteristics”. Waste characteristics are described by the biological, physical and chemical properties. These parameters are very important in waste landfills in order to categorize the wastages (Wijewardane, et al., 2014).

The constituents of the leachate formed from landfills are nutrients, biodegradable organic compounds, heavy metals, micro pollutants and microorganisms. The leachate has become a major hazard to the aquatic lives as well as it acts as a great risk to the human lives.

The characteristics of the leachate changes with the time. The contaminant concentration increase from an initial point to a maximum value and then decrease due to being either flushed out, precipitated or biodegraded (Rowe & Kerry, 1995). Therefore, remedial actions should be done in order to treat the ground water contaminated with the landfill-leachate. ‘Pump-and-treat’ systems are widely applied to treat the contaminated groundwater by landfill-leachate across the world. Pump- and- treat system includes a process of pumping the ground water from the subsurface to the treatment systems located on the ground surface. It leads to maintain a clean ground water flow and a hazard free environment (Council, 1994). As a result of the improvement of technology on landfill-leachate treatment, PRB’s were first introduced as an alternative method to pump- and- treat system in 1991 (Gillham, et al., 1994).

PRB treatment method is also known to be an in-situ treatment mechanism, which acts as a barrier to the groundwater contaminated with landfill-leachate. PRB is an in-situ treatment process, which is used to intersect a contaminated groundwater plume and treat it while the groundwater flows through the barrier. It is a new and most innovative technology method, which gives a good and inexpensive solution (Sewwandi, 2014).

There are various types of PRBs available in the world. The classifications are based on the reactive materials used inside the barriers of PRBs. They lead to produce biotic reactions or abiotic reactions. PRBs are filled with reactive materials, which have higher hydraulic conductivity than the soil surrounding the PRB (Di Nardo, et al., 2010). The ground water is forced to pass through the reactive packing media under the natural hydraulic gradient (Di Nardo, et al., 2010). Due to the various characteristics of the reactive packing materials, the constituents of the ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate are partially removed and it becomes partially cleaned.

PRBs are low-cost compared to the pump-and-treat methods. However, the conventional reactive media in PRBs such as zero valent ions and zeolite are quite expensive and associated with several issues including non-availability for frequent use. These conventional materials are frequently used to treat the groundwater contaminated with other sources, not the landfill-leachate (Ambrosini & Gianluca, 2004). Since the application of PRBs to treat the groundwater contaminated with landfill-leachate commenced recently, above-mentioned reactive materials may not have the potential to treat some contaminants in the landfill-leachate. Hence, the experiments on low-cost and readily available reactive materials targeting the contaminants found in landfill-leachate is a timely need. The landfill-leachate consists of different varieties of heavy metals, which are considered as priority pollutants (Council, 1994). Therefore, investigating low-cost reactive materials capable of treating heavy metals is of prime importance.

Building wastes is a controversial solid waste due to the lack of disposal sites. They are made of a number of chemical compounds, which may have the treatment potential for heavy metals. Dewatered Alum Sludge (DAS) has shown a considerable treatment potential for landfill-leachate (Dayanthi, et al., 2014). Hence it is expected that a mixture of building wastes and DAS would be a potential reactive media for PRBs to treat heavy metals in the groundwater contaminated with landfill-leachate.

1.2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1.2.1 Aim

The aim of this study is to investigate the heavy metal treatment potentials of building wastes and DAS using batch sorption experiments.

1.2.2 Objectives

The study has the following objectives:

- ✓ To determine the influences of adsorbent dosage and contact time for the adsorption of heavy metals on each of selected reactive material.
- ✓ To obtain the optimal adsorption capacity of each of selected reactive materials for different types of heavy metals.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

A series of batch experiments were conducted to optimize the removal efficiencies of heavy metals, namely Pb, Cd, Cu, Mn, Zn and As. The selected low-cost reactive materials include four types of building wastes, namely concrete waste (CW), bricks and mortar wastes (BW), flooring wastes (FW) and roofing wastes (RW); and DAS. Several series of batch experiments were conducted for each reactive material as adsorbent to optimize the contact time and adsorbent doses, and thereby to optimize the adsorption capacity of each reactive material for each type of heavy metal. The adsorption isotherms were plotted in order to obtain the adsorption characteristics.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

PRBs are used to treat the wastewater. Therefore in order to maintain the cost effectiveness of the project, the low-cost materials should be used as the reactive media in PRBs. The reactive materials that are used in the PRBs should be readily available because the reactive materials inside PRBs have to be replaced when the efficiency of treatment starts decreasing.

The building wastes are abundant in the present construction oriented world. According to the past studies, the building wastes such as bricks, roofs, timber etc. have good adsorption capacities. Therefore those materials is expected to perform well in treating the heavy metals in the ground water contaminated by landfill-leachate. DAS is also a readily available waste material.

Though there is a few research on recycling other types of wastes such as quarry dust, red sand, sea sand etc., the literature shows that recycling building wastes as reactive materials in PRBs aiming the landfill-leachate treatment is few or non-existent. Therefore it is expected that this study would come up with good outputs.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Ground water contamination by leachate which is produced by the solid waste dump sites has become a higher risk to Sri Lanka and other developing countries. The heavy metals in leachate are very harmful to human and the environment (Abhayawardana, 2015). Due to development of technology, PRBs are considered as a new technologist method in treating ground water contaminated by landfill-leachate. When designing PRB barrier it contains two methods. They are continuous trench and the funnel and gate system (Snow & David, 1999).

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram of the leachate production

Developing countries like Sri Lanka are having uncontrolled and unmanaged open dump sites. Due to that lots of environmental as well as social issues are created biological, chemical and physical reactions are taking place in landfills which creates landfill gases and leachates (Sewwandi, 2014). Leachate is formed when water gets contact with landfills. Water contaminates with landfills by either precipitation or percolation will pass through the decaying solid wastages in landfills and finally the leachate is formed beneath landfills.

Figure 2.2: Leachate formation

Figure 2.3: Leachate formed from Landfill

2.2 PERMEABLE REACTIVE BARRIER (PRB)

2.2.1 Definition of Permeable Reactive Barrier

Permeable Reactive Barriers is an in-situ treatment process which are used to treat the groundwater contaminant plume by intersecting to it. It is a new and most innovative technology method which gives a good and inexpensive solution (Sewwandi, 2014). There are various types of PRBs are available in the world. The classifications are based on the reactive materials used inside the barriers of PRBs. They lead to produce biotic reactions or abiotic reactions. Another classification can be made whether the aeration walls produce physical or biological reactions (Institute, 2012).

Figure 2.4: Schematic diagram of PRB

Batch experiments are described to screen and select the appropriate materials for use in PRB design trenches (Ahmed & Faisal, 2015). The reactive materials selection is mainly based on the geometrical condition of the site and contaminants of interest. The reactive medium used in PRBs are granular solid phase in order to make conditions in the substrate (Higgins & Monica, 2011).

A typical PRB has a treatment zone which is construction underground as a shape of a trench. It is constructed across the flow of the plume. Inside the trench the reactive materials are placed as granular form in order to increase the working efficiency (Ambrosini & Gianluca, 2004).

When the contaminated groundwater flows through the barrier, the materials retain or they transform the contaminants. Another important consideration should be taken about the quantity of the reactive materials that should be taken in the trenches (Ambrosini, 2004). Quantity depends on the removing rate of the contaminant to the desired level of concentration considering design year period.

2.2.2 PRB system configurations

(Snow & David, 1999) has shown that the design method of PRB walls can be categorized as are continuous trench and the funnel and gate system. For the field applications, PRB walls can be constructed with various methods. But preferably there are two major traditional methods. First one is continuous wall system and the second one is gate and funnel system (Bronstein & Kate, 2005). Each systems are described below;

2.2.2.1 Continuous PRB

Most common application is the continuous PRB construction. In a continuous PRB outline, the reactive media is distributed across the width and vertical extent of the groundwater contaminant plume (Council, 2011). The impacts on the natural groundwater flow can be minimized when the continuous PRB are properly designed. Unlike impermeable barrier walls, PRBs are not considered to avoid the flow of groundwater and, therefore, hypothetically do not need to be keyed into a low-permeability layer. It is good practice to key the PRB into an original low-permeability layer if one is present, to safeguard complete plume capture and as a protection in the event the permeability of the PRB is cooperated.

Figure 2.5: Continuous PRB

2.2.2.2 Funnel and gate system

A funnel-and-gate system uses low-permeability materials to make (funnel) the groundwater towards a permeable treatment zone (gate). Guiding the groundwater in the direction of a treatment gate may surge the natural groundwater flow velocity. Funnel-and-gate designs are essential to extend outside the extent of the plume to guarantee all contaminated groundwater is captured and treated.

Figure 2.6: Funnel and gate system

There are another two design of permeable reactive barriers are available in the field. Those are;

1. Injection wall configuration

Figure 2.7: Injection wall configuration

2. Passive collector with reaction walls

Figure 2.8: Passive collector

2.2.3 Installation of PRB in field

Most common installation method of PRB in field is the excavation method. The excavation method is also can be classified as unsupported excavation and supported excavation. Excavation methods can be done up to a depth of 8m beneath the top surface (Council, 2011). The excavation process is carried out by backhoes and construction procedure starts.

Figure 2.9: PRB installation at field

2.2.4 Advantages and disadvantages of PRB

2.2.4.1 Advantages

- PRB is operated in low cost unlike the pump and treat systems. The PRBs don't need any external energy inputs. They use the natural hydraulic gradient of ground water.
- Since it is an underground system, therefore other activities can be made on the ground.
- Large contaminants can be treated using PRB. Contaminant having low concentration level can be also treated.
- PRBs don't need any installation systems like pump and treat system. They don't need any surface operating structures like other systems.

2.2.4.2 Disadvantages

- For treating the contaminants the reactive media may not be suitable for that. Because it depends on the target contaminants to be removed.
- The plume should contain homogeneous matrix.
- Long term performances of PRBs may not suitable. Due to the reactions in the trench, permeability may loss.

- The plume depth from the ground should be a considerable amount. For the current technology it is suitable to have a depth of 15-20 meters.

2.3 REACTIVE MEDIA

PRBs should have a finest amount of reactive medium and also the media should have an essential residence time to treat the contaminants of ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate (Institute, 2012). There may various types of reduction process take place in the adsorbent. Especially when the concentration of heavy metals is low in landfill-leachate, preferably the “adsorption” process will be carried out in adsorbent (Abhayawardana, 2015).

As mentioned below mediums which are used in PRBs generally (Institute, 2012):

- ZVI is the commonly used media to treat the organic compounds in waste water.
- Recycled materials can form a permeable “bio wall” which are used to treat the organic compounds and heavy metals.
- Zeolites are normally used to treat the waste water having radionuclide.
- Organic substrates can be used as “bio barrier” in PRBs to treat waste water. Especially nutrients and vegetable oil are used as organic substrates.

2.3.1 Reactive Medias used in past studies

2.3.1.1 Risk husk (Al-Salihy, et al., 2016)

Batch sorption experiments were conducted by varying the mass of adsorbent by (Al-Salihy, et al., 2016). The experiments were carried out in 250 ml conical flasks and the total volume of the reaction mixture was kept at 100 ml. For each conical flasks the pH was remained as constant. The particle size kept here was (0.6-1.2) mm and series of mass of adsorbent were taken as (0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 3) g. Each supernatant were collected and filtered through membrane filter paper. According to the results Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms were checked. According to the adsorption values (Al-Salihy, et al., 2016) proved that low cost adsorbent rice husk is considerably efficient for the removal of Cd (II) from its solution.

Figure 2.10: Isotherm variations (Al-Salihy, et al., 2016)

From his experiment results, Freundlich isotherm has a better coefficient of determination (R^2) values than Langmuir isotherm. Therefore finally as a solution, Freundlich isotherm is a better for fitting with the experimental data.

2.3.1.2 Saw dust (BULUT Yasemin, 2007)

Batch and column sorption studies to removal Cd (ii) from aqueous solution was investigated by this researcher using sawdust from Triplochiton Scleroxylon. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models were applied to equilibrium data at four temperatures. Sorption studies were carried out by batch process in 250mL conical flasks. The equilibrium isotherms were determined by contacting fixed cadmium initial concentration $C_0= 100$ mg/L with different mass of sawdust (2 to 25g).

The Sawdust and cadmium solutions were poured in a series of flasks with equal volumes of solution (100 mL) for a period of 45 minutes at desired temperature. The series of flasks was agitated at a constant speed of 300 rpm in a water bath at temperatures 30, 40, 50 and 60°C, respectively. Sawdust from the samples was separated by vacuum filtration using 45µm membrane filters to remove the particulates and the filtrate was analyzed using a Varian AA 20 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer.

Another experiment setup was carried out by (BULUT Yasemin, 2007) by using saw dust for the sorption process. The adsorption of Lead, Cadmium and Nickel from aqueous solution by sawdust of walnut was investigated. The effect of contact time, initial metal ion concentration and temperature on metal ions removal has been studied. The equilibrium time was found to be of the order of 60 min (BULUT Yasemin, 2007).

Initially he carried out the kinematic experiments, i.e. the time optimization experiments. The graph indicated below shows the optimized time for each selected heavy metals.

Figure 2.11: Optimization of time (BULUT Yasemin, 2007)

He observed that the rate of HMI removal was attained after approximately 1 h stirring. According to the graph obtained, stirring time longer than 1 h doesn't seem to be much benefit. Therefore he used stirring time of 1 h for further studies. By developing adsorption isotherms; Langmuir isotherm & Freundlich isotherm, the removal rate of heavy metals ions were obtained. The selectivity order of the adsorbent is $\text{Pb(II)} \approx \text{Cd(II)} > \text{Ni(II)}$. According to the results above mentioned, it can be concluded that the sawdust of walnut could be a good adsorbent for the metal ions from aqueous solutions.

2.3.1.3 Fava beans (Etorki, et al., 2014)

Fava beans were used as adsorbent material for removal of Pb (II), Cd (II) and Zn (II) ions from aqueous solutions and wastewater samples. (Etorki, et al., 2014) had done the experiments in various categories. They are listed below;

- Effect of initial pH
- Effect of contact time
- Effect of adsorbent quantity
- Effect of initial metal ion concentration

The samples were prepared without further treatment and sorted according to the particles diameter by standard sieves 250 - 500 μm . The higher adsorption capacities were attained at pH 3.0 for Pb (II), pH 4.5 for Cd (II) and pH 4.0 for Zn (II) ions. For the optimized time he used 1.30 h at 175 r.p.m of magnetic shaker machine for (15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90 min). After analyzed using AAS each adsorption rate was identified and isotherms were

checked. Checks were made by this author to experiment results with the adsorption isotherms and finally it was concluded that the adsorption processes are well fitted with Langmuir isotherm. The corresponding graphs are shown below;

Figure 2.12: Isotherm analysis for heavy metals removal

2.3.1.4 Coconut husk (Emoruwa & Agbozu, 2014)

A set of batch experiments were carried out by using coconut husk as adsorbent by I.E. Agbozu (2014) in order to treat the heavy metals of Cu, Pb, Fe, Cr and Cd. Each heavy metals were analyzed by using the atomic adsorption spectrometer (AAS) by preparing the standard solutions in 250 ml volumetric flasks. Batch adsorption experiments were carried out at the room temperature (Emoruwa & Agbozu, 2014).

Adsorption experiment was done by measuring 50 ml of the waste water sample and poured into a 100 ml conical flask. 5 g of pre-treated fine particle coconut husk was added to the waste water. The different factors affecting adsorption process of the metal ions under study (Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Cr^{2+} and Cd^{2+}) such as contact time, concentration, adsorbent dose and pH have been studied.

Coconut husk also showed a positive result in adsorbing the heavy metals. The percentage of removal of metals increased with increasing weight (0.4 – 1.2) g in 50 ml of adsorbent dosage. The removal rate observed was $\text{Cr} > \text{Cu} > \text{Cd} > \text{Fe} > \text{Pb}$. The adsorption efficiency increased with initial metal ion concentration and the observed trend was $\text{Cr} > \text{Cu} > \text{Cd}$

> Fe > Pb. The percentage removal of metal ions increased with increasing pH of the mixed metal ions solution. The removal percentages of coconut husk for each heavy metals are as follows; Cd: 95.2-98.8 %, Cr: 91.1-99.3 %, Cu: 75.0-98.5 %, Fe: 84.9-97.0 % and Pb: 81.1-98.7 % (Emoruwa & Agbozu, 2014).

Similarly according to the past researches washed quarry dust (WQD), fly ash, zero valent iron (ZVI), zeolites, granular activated carbon (GAC), red sand, bio char, etc. show positive conclusions in removing heavy metals from aqueous solutions.

Some of the characteristics of the reactive packing media are given below (Bronstein & Kate, 2005);

- **Stability:** The reactive media needs to be existed in the PRBs for a considerable time period once there are continuous flow of the plume.
- **Reactivity:** The reaction rate of the reactive media is very important in designing the PRB walls. Because it determines the required residence time. Therefore it finally determines the size of the PRB walls.
- **Environmental compatibility:** For the reactive media, in order to minimize the plume flow across the PRB, the grain sizes of the reactive media is very important.
- **Hydraulic performance:** The reactive materials should have the permeability greater than the permeability of the aquifers in order to achieve the plume pass through the PRB walls.
- **Availability and cost:** The reactive materials should be readily available and they should be low cost.

2.4 EFFECT OF HEAVY METALS IN LEACHATE

In biological treatment of waste water microorganisms are considered as very important factors. Microbiological parameters such as weight, number and activities of microorganisms are good indicators of heavy metals in treating waste water. The amount of microorganisms depend on the content and concentrations of heavy metals contaminated with waste water. Heavy metals have a negative impact on the growth of microorganisms (Sa'idi & Majid, 2010).

2.4.1 Leachate composition

Municipal landfill leachate mainly consists large amount of organic and inorganic contaminants which provide severe environmental and health hazards (Sewwandi, 2014).

Here below the table illustrates constituents in a typical municipal landfill-leachate.

Table 2.1: Table of Constituents of Municipal landfill-leachate

Parameter	Value (mg/L)
Ph	7.2
Eh (mV)	329
CO ₂	62
A _{Stot}	10
SO ₄	562
Ca	99
Fe	0.4
K	22
Mg	64
Mn	0.4
Na	133
Si	3
Zn	0.1
Cl	73

2.5 LANDFILL-LEACHATE TREATMENT

There should be a proper remediation technology introduced in order to reduce the above harmful effects. The remediation technologies can be mainly classified into two principal categories (Park, et al., 2002):

- In-situ (treatments are carried in the ground)

These kind of treatment arrangement is done with contamination without removing polluted water or existing soil from the particular ground.

- Ex-situ (treatments are carried above the ground level)

These kind of treatment mechanisms need some excavation process to remove the existing soil and abstracting the polluted water to treat elsewhere.

2.6 ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS

“Adsorption” may be defined as the process of accumulation of any substance giving higher concentration of molecular species on the surface of another substance as compared to that in the bulk.

2.6.1 Adsorbate

The substance that concentrates at the surface is called adsorbate (Dada, et al., 2012).

2.6.2 Adsorbent

The material upon whose surface the adsorption takes place is called an adsorbent. Mostly activated carbon is used as an adsorbent (Dada, et al., 2012).

2.6.3 Freundlich Isotherm Model

Freundlich expressed an empirical equation for representing the isothermal variation of adsorption of a quantity of gas adsorbed by unit mass of solid adsorbent with pressure in 1909. This equation is known as Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm or Freundlich Adsorption equation or simply Freundlich Isotherm (Shodhganga, 2009).

$$\frac{x}{m} = K_f (C_e)^{1/n}$$

$$\text{Log} \left(\frac{x}{m} \right) = \frac{1}{n} \text{Log} (C_e) + \text{Log} (K_f)$$

Where,

x/m - Adsorption per gram of adsorbent which is obtained by dividing the amount of adsorbate (x) by the weight of the adsorbent (m).

C_e - Equilibrium concentration, k and n are constants whose values depend upon adsorbent and gas at particular temperature (mg/L).

K_f - Freundlich constant denoting adsorption capacity (mg/g)

$1/n$ - Adsorption intensity (L/mg)

Figure 2.13: Freundlich isotherm variation

2.6.4 Langmuir Isotherm Model

In 1916, Irving Langmuir published a new model isotherm for gases adsorbed to solids, which retained his name. It is a semi-empirical isotherm derived from a proposed kinetic mechanism (Shodhganga, 2009).

This isotherm was based on different assumptions one of which is that dynamic equilibrium exists between adsorbed gaseous molecules and the free gaseous molecules.

$$\frac{x}{m} = \frac{abCe}{1+bCe}$$

$$\frac{Ce}{x/m} = \frac{1}{ab} + \frac{Ce}{a}$$

Where,

x/m - Amount adsorbate adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent (q_e)

a, b - Empirical constants

C_e - Equilibrium concentration of adsorbate in solution after adsorption

Figure 2.14: Langmuir isotherm variation

2.6.5 Temkin Isotherm Model

Temkin isotherm indicates that the adsorption energy will decrease linearly with coverage. Temkin isotherm can be expressed in its linear form as follows (Banerjee, et al., 2013);

$$q_e = \frac{RT}{b} \text{Log} (K_T \times C_e)$$

$$q_e = \frac{RT}{b} \text{Log} (K_T) + \frac{RT}{b} \text{Log} (C_e)$$

Where,

R - Gas constant (8.314 J/mol/K)

T - Temperature (K)

K_T - Equilibrium binding constant corresponding to the maximum binding energy (L/mg)

C_e - Equilibrium concentration (mg/L)

Figure 2.15: Temkin isotherm variation

2.6.6 Elovich Isotherm Model

Elovich isotherm model is also another adsorption model which is widely used in many adsorption kinetics. This model describes the chemical adsorption (chemical reaction). There is also a linear relationship in this isotherm. The linearized formulae is given below (Inyang, et al., 2015);

$$\text{Log} \left(\frac{C_e}{q_e} \right) = \text{Log} (K_E q_m) - \frac{1}{qm} (q_e)$$

Where,

K_E - Elovich isotherm constant

C_e - Equilibrium concentration (mg/L)

Figure 2.16: Elovich isotherm variation

2.6.7 Dubinin – Radushkevich Isotherm Model

Dubinin–Radushkevich isotherm is generally applied to express the adsorption mechanism with a Gaussian energy distribution onto a heterogeneous surface (Dada, et al., 2012). The model has often successfully fitted high solute activities and the intermediate range of concentrations data well.

$$\ln (q_e) = \ln (q_m) - B \left\{ RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{C_e} \right) \right\}^2$$

Where,

- q_e - Amount of adsorbate in the adsorbent at equilibrium (mg/g)
- q_m - Theoretical isotherm saturation capacity (mg/g)
- R - Gas constant (8.314 J/mol/K)
- T - Absolute temperature (K)
- C_e - Adsorbate equilibrium concentration (mg/L)
- B - Empirical constant

Figure 2.17: Dubinin – Radushkevich isotherm variation

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 OVERALL PROCEDURE

Figure 3.1 shows the overall summarized procedure of this research. As shown above initially the raw materials collection was done in nearby building construction sites in Karapitiya, Galle. As planned in the methodology categorization and preparation of the raw materials were conducted in the department laboratory.

Figure 3.1: Overall procedure

10 times diluted landfill-leachate was the solution for all the batch experiments. The landfill-leachate was obtained from the municipal solid waste dumpsite in the Galle Municipal area. By diluting the raw landfill-leachate by 10 times, the concentration of the landfill-leachate was reduced to represent the contaminated groundwater by landfill-leachate.

After all the preliminary works, batch experiments were conducted for the raw materials that were collected for the research. First a series of batch experiments were conducted to optimize the time for each pair of heavy metal and reactive material. Then another set of batch experiments were conducted with the optimized time values to optimize the mass of adsorbent for each pair of heavy metal and reactive material.

Finally isotherms were plotted with each pair of heavy metal and reactive material to obtain the adsorption characteristics and capacities.

3.2 CATEGORIZATION OF REACTIVE MATERIALS

Building wastes belonging to four categories, namely CW, BMW, FW and RW, and DAS were selected as reactive materials. The rough contents of the selected building wastes are as follows:

- I. CW : Concrete and Reinforcement
- II. BMW : Bricks and Mortar
- III. FW : Floor tiles + Dried cement slurry
- IV. RW : Roof waste without asbestos + Timber

The above building wastes were collected from the construction work site of the Teaching Hospital, Karapitiya. DAS was obtained from the sludge drying bed of the Hapugala water treatment plant as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Sludge drying bed, Water treatment plant, Hapugala

The reactive materials have some properties.

❖ Physical Properties:

- Specific Gravity
- Particle Size Distribution
- Porosity
- Moisture Content Wet Weight Basis

❖ Mechanical Properties:

- Hydraulic Conductivity

- Shear Strength (Cohesion and Friction Angle)
- Electrical Conductivity

The removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions can be done in various methods. But here it is mainly considered that the heavy metals of diluted landfill leachate are mainly removed by “Adsorption” process. Therefore for this adsorption process there should be various constituents in those reactive materials. According to the literature review the constituents were identified and listed in the table below;

Table 3.1: Constituents of reactive materials

Materials Collected	Constituents of Materials
Concrete	Superplasticizers on Portland cement Z-Potentials of cement component minerals Admixtures of concrete Pigments, fibers and polymers High adsorption rate by aggregate which are bound together by hydrated cement
Cement Sand Mortar	Fly ash known as Pulverized fuel ash (pfa) Ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS) Sand is having PCE and BNS superplasticizer with different fineness and compositions Performance analysis of Sodium Sulphate and Magnesium Phosphate in cement mortar
Bricks	Rice Husk Ash Clay is the major component of bricks. They are hydrous aluminosilicates broadly defined as those minerals that make up the colloid fraction of soils, sediments, rocks and water and may be composed of mixtures of fine grained clay minerals. Clay has some minerals, that they remove high concentration of Pb^{2+} .
Ceramic Tiles	Clay sized crystals of minerals such as quartz and carbonates have higher rate of removing heavy metals from aqueous solutions.

Reinforcement	Iron oxides are having higher rate of adsorbing heavy metal element. Mainly Cr (VI) reduction rate is high by iron metals.
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3.3 MATERIAL PREPARATION

3.3.1 Reactive materials

According to categorization as shown above, brick wastages (BW), floor wastages (FW), roof wastages (RW) and concrete wastages (CW) were collected separately in some construction sites in Galle. Dewatered alum sludge (DAS) was collected from the dry sludge bed of Water Treatment Plant, Hapugala.

Several steps were carried out for the material preparation. The steps are described below;

- Step 1: The collected reactive materials were washed several times with tap water and allowed to dry in oven at 80⁰C – 100⁰C for 36h – 48h.
- Step 2: Hammering and grinding works were carried out manually in order to convert the larger particles in to smaller particles.
- Step 3: Particle size distribution test is a compulsory test that should be done before the experiments because various particle sizes may change the results of the experiments. To achieve this, sieve analysis test was carried out in the laboratory to collect the particles which passed through a sieve of 0.75μm or higher.

Figure 3.3: Sieve analysis test apparatus

- Step 4: The sieved materials were oven dried at 60⁰C for 6h. Then samples of each reactive material were kept in plastic-stopper bottles (containers).

Figure 3.4: Prepared reactive materials

3.3.2 Diluted Landfill Leachate

According to the aim of the research, it is proposed to treat the ground water which is contaminated with landfill-leachate. Practically the sample collection is not possible. Therefore the fresh leachate was diluted to 10 times with de-ionized water in order to simulate the ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate.

For the research the fresh leachate was collected from the municipal solid waste dumpsite at Heenpandala, Galle. Leachate was collected in the containers separately according to the age of the leachate available at the site. While collecting the samples special protective pieces of equipment were used. Heenpandala landfill is governed by Galle Municipal council.

Figure 3.5: Heenpandala landfill area

There were three ages of leachate available in the particular landfill area. They are listed below;

- i. Fresh leachate (A)
- ii. Leachate less than 20 years (B)
- iii. Leachate more than 30 years (C)

Figure 3.6: Instantaneous landfill leachate categories

Figure 3.7: Collection of Leachate

Soon after the collected leachate samples arrived at the site, initial parameters such as pH and temperature were measured by using the pH meter and thermometer and noted down. The measured values for each collected leachate samples are listed below.

Table 3.2: pH and temperature values of leachate samples

Leachate	pH	Temperature (°C)
Fresh	8.32	31.9

3.4 BATCH SORPTION EXPERIMENTS

3.4.1 Overall methodology of batch sorption experiments

1. Kinematic experiments

Initially kinematic experiments were carried out in order to optimize the time. This was achieved by taking a predetermined mass and volume of adsorbate and adsorbent. Then by conducting the adsorption experiments for several time values. The removal efficiency was plotted against contact time (Figure 3.8) to find out the optimum contact time for each pair of heavy metal and adsorbent (reactive material).

Figure 3.8: Obtaining optimum parameter

2. Adsorption isotherm experiments

After the kinematic experiments the adsorption isotherm experiments were conducted by using the above optimum time values. For each pair of heavy metal and adsorbent (reactive material). This was done by conducting a batch experiment for each pair by varying the mass of adsorbent and keeping the contact time constant at the relevant optimum value obtained in the previous test. Then the removal efficiency was plotted against the mass of adsorbent (Figure 3.8) to optimize the mass.

3.4.2 A typical example for the batch sorption experiment procedure

An example for the procedure of the batch sorption experiments for each pair of heavy metal and adsorbent (reactive material) is described below:

- Step 1: The landfill leachate which was preserved in the refrigerator was cooled down for the atmospheric temperature.
- Step 2: A set of adsorbent weights were measured by using the electronic balance and by using the watch glass.
- Step 3: Required no of conical flasks were taken for each samples and the measured adsorbents will be inserted into the conical flasks. Before that each conical flasks were washed with tap water and then with distilled water.
- Step 4: A same volume of 250ml, 10 times diluted landfill-leachate sample was measured by using the measuring cylinder and was poured into each conical flasks.
- Step 5: Each conical flasks were placed with magnets and were placed in the magnetic stirrer machines.
- Step 6: 24 hour continuous stirring was conducted for each samples at 200 r.p.m speed. This was done for the early two trial experiments. But for the time optimization experiments, each magnetic stirrer machines were stirred for the allocated time period and for the mass optimization experiments all stirrer machines were stirred for the time which was obtained from the time optimization experiments.
- Step 7: After the stirring all the test samples were kept for some time period in order to allow the settlement of the reactive material.
- Step 8: After that all test samples were filtered by using the membrane filter method and were kept in the sample bottles. For the filtration process 0.45 μ m glass fiber filter paper was used. Filtration process was carried using membrane vacuum pump.

Figure 3.9: Membrane filter technique using vacuum pump

- Step 9: Each analysis was conducted by using the samples in the bottles.

Figure 3.10: Bottling and labelling the supernatant samples

3.4.3 Testing Parameters

Table 3.4 depicts the wastewater parameters were measured for each filtered samples.

Table 3.3: Wastewater parameters to be measured

Parameter	Unit	Apparatus
Heavy metals: Fe (An abundant heavy metal in leachate) Pb, Cd, Cu, Mn, Zn and As	mg/L	Atomic adsorption spectrophotometer
Conductivity	$\mu\text{S/cm}$	Conductivity meter
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) – It is a measure of all dissolved solids which may include all heavy metals.	mg/L	Total dissolved solid removal
Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP)	mV	ORP meter
pH	-	pH meter

3.4.4 Trial batch experiments conducted

3.4.4.1 Trial experiment 1

Initially trial experiments were conducted in order to check the possible ranges of the contact time and mass of adsorbent which are applicable to the selected pairs of heavy metal and adsorbent (reactive material). Therefore for the first trial experiment dewatered

alum sludge was used. For this process 7 no of samples were taken as a trial mass series as 1g, 5g, 10g, 20g, 30g, 40g, 50g. The 1st trial experiment set up is shown below;

Figure 3.11: Trial experiment setup for typical waste material

Figure 3.12: Setup for 1st Trial experiment

The above batch experiment was carried out continuously for 24 hours. As mentioned in the methodology part, each necessary steps were carried out after the stirring period and necessary analysis were carried out. The analysis is shown in section 3.4.4.1.

Table 3.4: Weight of adsorbent considered for Trial 1

Sample	Weight of DAS (g)
1	1
2	5
3	10
4	20
5	30
6	40
7	50

3.4.4.2 Trial experiment 2

2nd trial experiment was done using floor wastages (FW). For this process 5 no of samples were taken as 2g, 4g, 6g, 8g, and 10g. Here the weight of adsorbent were taken is very low. Because due to the large amount of weight in the 1st trial experiments problems were occurred while stirring by magnets. The 2nd trial experiment set up is shown below;

Figure 3.13: Setup for 2nd Trial experiment

Table 3.5: Adsorbent weight of FW

Sample	Weight of FW (g)
1	2
2	4
3	6
4	8
5	10

After the 2 trial experiments and according to the analysis of the above trial experiments, time optimization experiments (Kinematic experiments) were proposed.

3.4.5 Time optimization experiments (Kinematic experiments)

Time optimization experiments were carried out by maintaining same amount of adsorbent in each conical flasks. Here in these experiments the changing parameter is the time of stirring by the magnetic stirrers for each conical flasks. Each conical flasks were stirred with various time period. Finally by plotting the graph of the removal efficiency vs time stirred, the optimum time for the selected reactive material was obtained. Optimum time was selected corresponding to the maximum removal efficiency value. The time optimization experiments conducted for each reactive materials are given below.

Figure 3.14: Kinematic experiment samples

3.4.5.1 Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

Initially set of 10g of prepared DAS powder were measured using electronic balance. The set of conical flasks were taken and for each the measured DAS powder were placed. Then to each samples 250ml of preserved diluted leachate sample was measured and poured. After that magnets were placed in each samples. Before placing the samples in the magnetic stirrers, the temperature and the speed of the rotation were adjusted. For this process temperature was maintained as 0⁰C (Sample was still in the room temperature) and 200 r.p.m was maintained. Then the experiment setup was started to stir. The experiment setup is shown below;

Figure 3.15: Setup for kinematic experiment by DAS

Table 3.5: Time of stirring for DAS of kinematic experiment

Sample	Time of stirring (hrs)
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	6
6	15

3.4.5.2 Floor waste (FW), Brick waste (BW), Roof waste (FW) and Concrete waste (CW)

The procedure is same as mentioned in the section 3.4.5.1. Here instead of having 15 hour sample it was carried out with 12 hours for these reactive materials.

Table 3.6: Time of stirring for other materials

Sample	Time of stirring (hrs)
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	6
6	12

3.4.6 Mass optimization experiments (Adsorption isotherm experiments)

After conducted the time optimization experiments for each reactive materials, mass optimization experiments were started for each selected reactive materials. For these experiments the changing parameter in the amount of adsorbent taken in each conical flasks. Here the time for the stirring process for each reactive materials were selected as the time obtained from the time optimization experiments for the appropriate reactive materials. Finally by plotting the graph of removal efficiency vs the mass of the adsorbent, the optimum mass were obtained corresponding to the maximum removal efficiency value. The mass optimization experiments for each reactive materials are given below;

3.4.6.1 Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

Initially set of 2.5g, 5g, 10g, 15g and 20g of prepared DAS powder were measured using electronic balance. The set of conical flasks were taken and for each the measured DAS powder were placed. Then to each samples 250ml of preserved diluted leachate sample

was measured and poured. After that magnets were placed in each samples. Before placing the samples in the magnetic stirrers, the temperature and the speed of the rotation were adjusted. For this process temperature was maintained as 0⁰C (Sample was still in the room temperature) and 200 r.p.m was maintained. Then the experiment setup was started to stir. The experiment setup is shown below;

Figure 3.16: Setup for DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Table 3.7: Weight of adsorbent considered for DAS mass optimization

Sample	Weight of adsorbent (g)
1	2.5
2	5
3	10
4	15
5	20

This same experiment setup was used for Floor waste (FW) and Concrete waste (CW) as well.

3.4.6.2 Brick waste (BW)

The procedure was same as described in the section 3.4.6.1. But the set of adsorbent were taken as 2.5g, 5g, 7.5g, 10g and 15g. The experiment set up is shown below;

Figure 3.17: Setup for BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Table 3.8: Weight of adsorbent considered for BW mass optimization

Sample	Weight of adsorbent (g)
1	2.5
2	5
3	7.5
4	10
5	15

3.4.6.3 Roof waste (RW)

The procedure was same as described in the section 3.4.6.1. But the set of adsorbent were taken as 2.5g, 5g, 10g, 12g and 15g. The experiment set up is shown below;

Figure 3.18: Setup for RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Table 3.9: Weight of adsorbent considered for RW mass optimization

Sample	Weight of adsorbent (g)
1	2.5
2	5
3	10
4	12
5	15

3.5 ANALYSIS

3.5.1 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

In the ground water naturally there are some metal ions contaminated. These ions slowly dissolve from soil particles, sediments, and rocks as the water travels along mineral surfaces in the pores or fractures of the unsaturated zone and the aquifer. These are known as the dissolved solids.

Therefore Total dissolved solids (TDS) analysis is an important parameter that was considered in this research. The calculation procedure for analyzing the TDS in the supernatant is given below:

$$\text{Total dissolved solids (g)} = \text{Residue after evaporation (g)} - \text{Initial weight of Petri dish (g)}$$

$$\text{Concentration of TDS (mg/L)} = \text{Total dissolved solids (mg)} / \text{Volume of Supernatant (L)}$$

Figure 3.19: Petri dishes with supernatant for TDS analysis

3.5.2 Conductivity, pH and ORP analysis

After the collection of supernatant the conductivity, pH and ORP values were measured for the trial experiments as conducted at the start of this research. The above three values were directly measured from the corresponding instruments.

The pictures shown below describes the methods of measuring the parameters.

Figure 3.20: Measuring pH values (i) and measuring conductivity values (ii) of the supernatants

The instruments used for the above analysis are shown below;

Figure 3.21: Conductivity meter (i), pH meter (ii) & ORP meter (iii)

3.5.3 Heavy metals

According to the aim of this research, it is required to obtain the removal efficiency of some heavy metals which are contaminated with the diluted leachate. For this process here the table shows the heavy metals that were analyzed and the corresponding instrument used for this process;

Table 3.10: Instruments used for heavy metals analysis

Heavy metal	Instrument
Fe	Spectrophotometer
Cd	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer
Zn	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer
Mn	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer
Cu	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer
Pb	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer
As	Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer

The removal efficiency for each heavy metals was calculated by using the formula given below;

$$\text{Removal efficiency} = \frac{(\text{Influent concentration} - \text{Effluent concentration})}{\text{Influent concentration}}$$

Figure 3.22: Samples preserved for heavy metal analysis

3.5.3.1 Fe analysis

For the analysis of Fe, the spectrophotometer was used in the laboratory. Therefore for this process initially there was a requirement to construct the standard calibration curve for Fe analysis. Therefore initially Fe standard solutions were prepared. The procedure explained below shows the steps involved in the Fe standard preparation (Pittsburgh, 2005).

Part I: Preparation of standards

1. 0.7022g grams of ferrous ammonium sulfate hexahydrate was dissolved in distilled water. This solution was diluted to 1L. This solution was 100 mg/L Fe^{2+} (same as 100 ppm). Sodium acetate was used as buffer to maintain a constant pH, in order to prevent Fe^{2+} being oxidized to Fe^{3+} .
2. Standard solutions of 0.0, 2.0, 4.0, 6.0 and 8.0 ppm were prepared by respectively diluting 0.0, 2.0, 4.0, 6.0 and 8.0 mL of the 100 ppm stock solution into five separate 100 mL volumetric flasks. To each flask 5 mL of a 0.25% ortho-phenanthroline solution was added. Then they were diluted with deionized water to 100 mL.
3. Set of cuvetts were cleaned, dried and labelled. After that each cuvetts were filled with appropriate solution.

The picture below shows the standard solutions prepared and the Fe^{2+} stock solution.

Figure 3.23: Standards prepared for Fe analysis

Part II: Preparation of the unknown

1. Each unknown samples for Fe analysis were collected.
2. After that 5 mL of the 0.25% ortho-phenanthroline solution was added to a 100 mL volumetric flask.
3. Then the above sample was diluted by the unknown sample to the mark.

Part III: Forming standard calibration curve

1. Each standard solutions and prepared unknown samples were tested using spectrophotometer. For this process wave length was adjusted to 510nm.

Figure 3.24: Spectrophotometer

2. Initially one cuvet was filled with blank and the instrument was set to 0 absorbance.
3. After that each prepared solutions and samples were measured with their absorbance values. The table below shows the absorbance values obtained for the standard solutions.

Table 3.11: Absorbance values from spectrophotometer

Std. Concentration (mg/L)	Absorbance (A)
0	0.002
2	0.375
4	0.768
6	1.178
8	1.541

The graph below shows the Fe standard calibration curve according to the above absorbance values. This graph was used for the determination of concentration of iron in the unknown samples.

Figure 3.25: Standard calibration curve for Fe analysis

3.5.3.2 Cd, Zn, Mn, Cu, Pb and As analysis

Other metals except Fe were analyzed using Atomic Adsorption Spectrometer (AAS). For this analysis also the standard solutions were prepared for each heavy metals using the standard stock solutions.

Figure 3.26: Stock standards and micro-pipette

The initial concentrations of these standard solutions were randomly selected. According to that using micro pipettes the standard solutions were prepared. The table below shows the concentrations of standard solutions were selected for each heavy metal analysis.

Table 3.12: Standard solutions ranges for heavy metals

Heavy metal	Concentrations of Standard solutions (ppb)
Cd	10, 20, 30, 40
Zn	10, 20, 30, 40
Mn	10, 20, 30, 40
Cu	50, 100, 150, 200
Pb	10, 20, 30, 40
As	10, 20, 30, 40, 100, 200

Figure 3.27: Standard curves obtained from AAS

Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) is a technique for measuring quantities of chemical elements present in environmental samples by measuring the absorbed radiation by the chemical element of interest. For this experiment the usage of this atomic adsorption spectrometer is high (Báez, 2012).

This is done by reading the spectra produced when the sample is excited by radiation. The atoms absorb ultraviolet or visible light and make transitions to higher energy levels. Atomic absorption methods measure the amount of energy in the form of photons of light that are absorbed by the sample (Báez, 2012). A detector measures the wavelengths of light transmitted by the sample, and compares them to the wavelengths which originally passed through the sample.

**Figure 3.28: Atomic
Adsorption Spectrometer**

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter includes all the results for the trial experiments, time optimization experiments and mass optimization experiments conducted. The results include the variation in pH, conductivity, ORP and heavy metals removal efficiency for each experiment samples.

4.1 pH

4.1.1 Trial experiments

4.1.1.1 Trial Experiment 1 – Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

Figure 4.1: pH variation for samples of Trial 1

According to the graph as shown in Figure 4.1, there is a slight decrease in the pH values of the treated samples from the influent value. In the intermediate level there is a high decrease in the pH values. Refer Appendix A.1 for more details

4.1.1.2 Trial Experiment 2- Floor Waste (FW)

Figure 4.2: pH variation for samples of Trial 2

The variation of pH values in the above Figure 4.2 is not as a proper shape. The graph is still increasing. i.e. pH values of the treated effluents are higher than influent. Refer Appendix A.2 for more details

4.1.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 4.3: pH variation for reactive materials of mass optimization

There is a fall in the pH values for the treated effluents for DAS, BW, RW and CW as shown in the graphs above. Therefore according to the Figure 4.3, FW doesn't show a continuous fall in the pH values because ultimately there is a slight increase in the pH value for the treated effluent. The corresponding pH values are illustrated in Appendix A.

4.2 CONDUCTIVITY

4.2.1 Trial Experiments

4.2.1.1 Trial Experiment 1 - Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

Figure 4.4: Conductivity variation for Trial 1

The conductivity values of the treated effluents show a deviation from the influent conductivity value as shown in the Figure 4.4. They don't show a particular shape. Refer Appendix B.1 for more details

4.2.1.2 Trial Experiment 2 – Floor waste (FW)

Figure 4.5: Conductivity variation for Trial 2

Figure 4.5 shows an increase in the conductivity values of treated effluent of floor waste samples than influent conductivity value. Refer Appendix B.2 for more details.

4.2.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 4.6: Conductivity variation for Mass optimization experiments

Figure 4.6 shows a gradual decrease in the conductivity values of the treated effluents than influent for each reactive materials. Conductivity was measured in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The corresponding conductivity values are shown in Appendix B.3.

4.3 OXIDATION REDUCTION POTENTIAL (ORP)

4.3.1 Trial Experiments

4.3.1.1 Trial Experiment 1 – Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

Figure 4.7: ORP variation for Trial 1

There is not much deviation in the effluent values from the influent value as shown in Figure 4.7. It seems that effluent ORP values are much similar to the influent ORP value. But in some cases the effluent samples got ORP values greater than the influent value (sample 7). Refer Appendix C.1 for more details

4.3.1.2 Trial Experiment 2 – Floor waste (FW)

Figure 4.8: ORP variation for Trial 2

Figure 4.8 shows a gradual decrease in the oxidation reduction potential values. Each and every treated effluents have ORP values lesser than influent value. Refer Appendix C.2 for more details

4.3.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 4.9: ORP variation for Mass optimization

Each reactive materials show a rapid decrease in ORP values of the treated effluents initially as shown in Figure 4.9. But after the initial point there is a small decrease in the ORP values of the samples. The corresponding ORP values are shown in Appendix C.3.

4.4 TOTAL DISSOLVED SOLIDS (TDS)

4.4.1 Kinematic experiments

TDS analysis were carried out for each reactive materials as shown in the Figure 4.10 below. When analyzing the graph some of the TDS values were come with negative values. The reason for the problem is the supernatant were not taken using pipette. Specially TDS values for DAS samples were undergone with negative values which were conducted initially. After that the supernatant samples were taken by using pipette. FW and BW samples show a rapid rise in the early stage and finally it goes with approximately a constant value. RW and CW samples show a greater reduction in the removal of dissolved solids as shown the below figure.

Figure 4.10: TDS analysis for Time optimization

4.4.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 4.11: TDS analysis for Mass optimization

For the adsorption isotherm experiments also the total dissolved solids removal don't show a proper distribution. FW and BW samples have a high removal efficiency for total dissolved solids than other reactive materials.

Finally according to the results based on the total dissolved solids removal for both kinematic and adsorption isotherm experiments, it shows that it is not an efficient parameter to obtain the optimized time and mass. Because according to the variation in both cases as shown in the above graphs, it is very difficult to obtain the optimized values of time and mass. For the reference the calculated values are shown in Appendix D.8.

4.5 HEAVY METALS REMOVAL

Landfill leachate has so many heavy metals which are contaminated within it. Once it mixes with ground water, the ground water gets heavy metals from landfill leachate. Therefore PRB system is used to treat the heavy metals contaminated with landfill leachate. For this process it important to evaluate the removal efficiencies of heavy metals by the selected reactive materials as single media. At this stage heavy metals such as Fe, Cd, Zn, Mn, Cu, Pb and As were measured. Calculated removal efficiencies of Fe, Cd, Zn, Mn, Cu, Pb and As are shown in Appendix E-F.

4.5.1 Kinematic Experiments

As mentioned above initially kinematic experiments were conducted for a pre-determined mass of 10g for each samples. The corresponding removal efficiencies of each heavy metals as mentioned above were measured. The variation of the removal efficiencies of each heavy metals are shown in the sections below.

4.5.1.1 Fe analysis

Figure 4.12: Fe analysis for Time optimization

According to the Figure 4.12 the optimized time can be obtained when the variation of removal efficiency goes a constant value (i.e. the maximum removal efficiency of Fe by the reactive material). DAS has the optimum time of 6 hour where the removal efficiency of approximately 45%. Similarly all other reactive materials like FW, BW, RW and CW also show the optimized time of 6 hour with the removal efficiencies of nearly 66%, 80%, 20% and 65%. Calculated values are shown in Appendix E.

4.5.1.2 Cd analysis

Figure 4.13: Cd analysis for Time optimization

As shown in the Figure 4.13 above, the optimized time for each reactive materials are given below. DAS, FW, BW and RW have the optimum time of 6 hour where the approximate removal efficiencies are 70%, 98%, 51% and 40% respectively. CW shows an optimum time of 8 hour while the removal efficiency of Cd is approximately 52%. Calculated values are shown in Appendix E.

4.5.1.3 Zn analysis

According to the Figure 4.14 shown below, the optimized time values which are obtained are given below. The reactive materials except CW, have the optimum time of 6 hour with approximate removal efficiency of 44% for DAS, 43% for FW, 39% for BW and again 43% for RW. CW has the removal efficiency of 43% where the optimum time is 4 hour. Calculated values are shown in Appendix E.

Figure 4.14: Zn analysis for Time optimization

4.5.1.4 Mn analysis

Figure 4.15: Mn analysis for Time optimization

Above Figure 4.15 illustrates the removal of Mn. The optimized times obtained from the above figure for each materials are given below. DAS has the maximum removal efficiency of 55% achieved in 6 hour. FW has the maximum removal efficiency of 65%

achieved in 4 hour. BW has the maximum removal efficiency of 55% achieved in 4 hour. RW has the maximum removal efficiency of 50% achieved in 4 hour. Finally CW has the removal efficiency of 55% achieved in 6 hour. Calculated values are shown in Appendix E.

4.5.1.5 Cu analysis

Figure 4.16: Cu analysis for Time optimization

Above Figure 4.16 illustrates the removal of Cu. The optimized times obtained from the above figure for each materials are given below. The maximum removal efficiency of Cu by DAS is 43% which is achieved in 4 hour. The FW has a maximum removal efficiency of 38% achieved in 6 hour. The optimum time for BW is 6 hour where the maximum removal efficiency is 38%. RW and CW have maximum removal efficiencies if 38% where the optimum time of 6 hour. Calculated values are shown in Appendix E.

4.5.1.6 Pb analysis

For each reactive materials except RW, the removal efficiency of Pb is very high as shown in the Figure 4.17. The optimum time values and the maximum removal efficiencies are given below. The optimum time of DAS is 6 hour corresponding removal efficiency is 76%. FW has the maximum removal efficiency of 78% which is achieved in 6 hour. BW and CW have similar removal efficiency of 78% achieved in 6 hour. Finally RW have a

low removal efficiency of 33% among all other reactive materials and the optimum time achieved is 6 hour. All the calculations are shown in Appendix E.

Figure 4.17: Pb analysis for Time optimization

4.5.1.7 As analysis

Figure 4.18: As analysis for Time optimization

The removal efficiency of As by the selected reactive materials are shown in the Figure 4.18. The maximum removal efficiencies by each reactive materials are given; DAS, FW,

BW, RW and CW has the maximum removal efficiencies of 35%, 45%, 42%, 65% and 51% respectively. The corresponding optimum time achieved for all reactive materials is 6 hour.

A summary table is attached containing all heavy metals removal by each selected reactive materials in Appendix G.1 for further reference. This table include the maximum removal efficiencies in each case and the corresponding optimum time.

The chart below shows the maximum efficiencies of each heavy metals achieved by each selected reactive materials. This chart is the summary of Appendix G.1.

Figure 4.19: Removal efficiency variation at the optimum contact time (From kinematic experiments)

The high removable of each heavy metals by appropriate reactive materials at the kinematic experiment stage are listed in the Table 4.1 below. The below values are directly abstracted from the Figure 4.19 above.

Table 4.1: The type of heavy metal best removed by different reactive materials at the optimum contact time (From kinematic experiments)

Time Optimization		
Reactive material	Heavy metal	Removal Efficiency %
DAS	Pb	76.55
FW	Cd	98.28
BW	Fe	79.56
RW	As	65.15
CW	Pb	77.69

Table 4.2 below shows the best appropriate reactive material for each heavy metal removal. The values are directly obtained from Figure 4.19 shown above.

Table 4.2: Best reactive material for different heavy metals at the optimum contact time

Time Optimization		
Heavy metal	Reactive material	Removal Efficiency %
Fe	BW	79.56
Cd	FW	98.28
Zn	DAS	44.49
Mn	FW	67.16
Cu	DAS	43.44
Pb	BW	78.14
As	RW	65.15

The optimum time obtained from the analysis is shown in the Table 4.3 below. According to the methodology, these optimum times were used for adsorption isotherm experiments. That was the contact time for each corresponding reactive materials.

Table 4.3: Selected optimum time for each reactive material

Reactive material	Optimum time (hrs)
DAS	6
FW	6
BW	6
RW	6
CW	6

4.5.2 Adsorption isotherm experiments

After conducted the kinematic experiments, the adsorption isotherm experiments were conducted. For conducting adsorption isotherm experiments, the optimum time was selected for stirring of each samples for each selected reactive materials. As mentioned in the methodology, a trial mass series was selected and according to that the optimum masses were determined.

The sections given below describes the optimum mass obtained from each heavy metal analysis for each reactive materials. Here also the optimum mass is obtained after the variation comes to a constant corresponding maximum removal efficiency of heavy metal.

4.5.2.1 Fe analysis

Figure 4.20: Fe analysis for Mass optimization

According to the Figure 4.20 as shown above, all the variations show a constant shape. DAS and FW show the maximum efficiencies of 37% and 52% achieved at an optimum mass of 10g. BW has 90% achieved at 10g. Other materials like RW and CW have the removal efficiencies of 50% and 89% at 12g and 15g of optimum masses respectively.

4.5.2.2 Cd analysis

Figure 4.21: Cd analysis for Mass optimization

According to the Figure 4.21 as shown above all the reactive materials have a good removing efficiency of heavy metals as a small adsorbent mass value. The maximum removing efficiency and the optimum mass are shown below. DAS, FW, BW, RW and CW show the maximum removing efficiency of Cd are 67%, 68%, 75%, 70% and 70% respectively which are achieved at the optimum masses of 10g, 15g, 10g, 15g and 15g respectively. All the necessary calculations are shown in Appendix F.

4.5.2.3 Zn analysis

As shown in the Figure 4.22 below, Zn removable efficiency for each reactive materials has lower values than Cd removable efficiency. DAS has the maximum removing efficiency in removing Zn than other reactive materials where it has 68% of removing efficiency which is achieved at 20g of optimum mass. FW has the maximum removing efficiency of 52% at 15g of adsorbent mass. BW, RW and CW have similar removing efficiency value of 54% achieved at the optimum mass of 15g. Calculations are shown in Appendix F.

Figure 4.22: Zn analysis for Mass optimization

4.5.2.4 Mn analysis

For Mn removing except CW, all other reactive materials show a lower removing efficiency values according to the Figure 4.23 shown below. Where DAS shows a removing efficiency of 50% at the optimum mass of 15g. FW and BW have similar removal efficiency values of 53% at the masses of 15g and 10g respectively. 58% removing efficiency is achieved by RW at a mass value of 12g. Finally CW has the highest removing value of 78% which is achieved at the optimum mass of 15g. Necessary calculations are shown in Appendix F.

Figure 4.23: Mn analysis for Mass optimization

4.5.2.5 Cu analysis

Figure 4.24: Cu analysis for Mass optimization

All reactive materials have very low removing capacity of Cu than other heavy metals as shown in the Figure 4.24 above. DAS has removal efficiency of 32% achieved at an adsorbent mass of 10g. FW shows the least value among others where the removing efficiency value of 27% achieved 15g of adsorbent mass. BW and CW show a similar removing efficiency of 33% at the optimum masses of 10g and 15g respectively. RW has the highest removing efficient value of 37% achieved at the mass of 12g. Calculations are shown in Appendix F.

4.5.2.6 Pb analysis

In overall situation Pb removing by each reactive materials is higher than other heavy metals as shown in the Figure 4.25 below. Even at the small adsorbent mass value it shows high removing efficiency values for all reactive materials. DAS and CW show the maximum similar removing efficiency value of 69% than other materials at the optimum mass value of 15g. FW shows a removing efficiency value of 65% at the mass of 10g. BW has the lowest value of 48% has the optimum mass of 15g. RW has a removing efficiency value of 62% at a mass of 12g. All necessary calculations are attached in Appendix F.

Figure 4.25: Pb analysis for Mass optimization

4.5.2.7 As analysis

According to the Figure 4.26 shown below, As is the second lowest removable heavy metal for all reactive materials. DAS has the lowest efficiency value of 38% achieved at a mass of 15g. 43% removing efficiency value is achieved at the optimum mass of 20g by FW. BW has the maximum removing efficiency value of 48% at a mass value of 15g. RW and CW have the removing efficiency values of 40% and 45% respectively. These values are achieved at the optimum mass of 15g for each. All calculations are attached in Appendix F.

Figure 4.26: As analysis for Mass optimization

A summary table is attached containing all heavy metals removal by each selected reactive materials in Appendix G.2 for further reference. This table include the maximum removal efficiencies in each case and the corresponding optimum mas.

The chart below shows the maximum efficiencies of each heavy metals achieved by each selected reactive materials. This chart is the summary of Appendix G.2.

Figure 4.27: Variation of the best removal efficiencies at the optimum mass

The high removable of each heavy metals by appropriate reactive materials at the adsorption isotherm experiment stage are listed in the Table 4.4 below. The below values are directly abstracted from the Figure 4.27 above.

Table 4.4: The type of heavy metal best removed by different reactive materials at the optimum masses

Mass Optimization		
Reactive material	Heavy metal	Removal Efficiency %
DAS	Pb	69.39
FW	Cd	67.84
BW	Fe	90.89
RW	Cd	70.24
CW	Fe	89.84

Table 4.5 below shows the best appropriate reactive material for each heavy metal removal. The values are directly obtained from Figure 4.27 shown above.

Table 4.5: The type of reactive materials best suited for the removal of different types of heavy metals at the optimum masses

Mass Optimization		
Heavy metal	Reactive material	Removal Efficiency %
Fe	BW	90.89
Cd	BW	75.56
Zn	DAS	68.38
Mn	CW	78.15
Cu	DAS	39.72
Pb	DAS	69.39
As	BW	48.6

The optimum mass obtained from the analysis is shown in the Table 4.6 below. Ultimately the obtained optimum masses for each reactive materials are listed below.

Table 4.6: Optimum masses for different reactive materials

Reactive material	Optimum mass (g)
DAS	15
FW	20
BW	15
RW	15
CW	15

4.6 PLOTTING ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS

According to the experiment results and analysis, more than 90% of experiment analysis show that the adsorption process is much fitted with Langmuir isotherm with high accuracy. All the experiment results were checked with Freundlich isotherm. But they were not fitted with the isotherm. The experiment results which were not fitted well with Langmuir isotherm, were checked with Temkin isotherm and they were fitted well with Temkin isotherm. The section 4.6.1 below describes the isotherms models checked for adsorption of each heavy metals by selected reactive materials and the isotherm constants.

4.6.1 Adsorption isotherm experiments

4.6.1.1 Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

Figure 4.28: Isotherm variations of DAS samples of Mass optimization

Table 4.7: Isotherm constants of DAS samples of Mass optimization

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Langmuir isotherm constants			
		a (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R ²	x/m (mg/g)
DAS	Fe	47.169	1.493	0.9198	30.154
	Cd	384.615	0.184	1	2.702
	Zn	285.714	0.086	0.9755	1.456
	Mn	232.558	0.056	0.9995	0.866
	Cu	70.922	0.015	0.9923	0.145
	Pb	357.143	0.049	0.9996	2.274
	As	80.645	0.024	0.9653	0.161

Adsorption process of removal of each heavy metal by DAS are well fitted with Langmuir isotherm. Isotherm constants are shown in the Table 4.12 above.

4.6.2.2 Floor waste (FW)

Figure 4.29: Isotherm variations of FW samples of Mass optimization

Table 4.8: Isotherm constants of FW samples of Mass optimization

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Langmuir isotherm constants			
		a (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R ²	x/m (mg/g)
FW	Fe	103.093	2.064	0.9459	73.211
	Cd	384.615	0.189	0.9982	2.775
	Zn	192.308	0.056	0.9945	0.639
	Mn	256.41	0.061	0.9997	2.118
	Cu	28.986	0.011	0.9327	0.043
	Pb	303.03	0.04	0.999	1.577
	As	92.593	0.027	0.9887	0.207

Adsorption process of removal of each heavy metal by FW are well fitted with Langmuir isotherm as shown in the Table 4.13 above.

4.6.2.3 Brick waste (BW)

Figure 4.30: Isotherm variations of BW samples of Mass optimization

Table 4.9: Isotherm constants of BW samples of Mass optimization

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Langmuir isotherm constants			
		a (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R ²	x/m (mg/g)
BW	Fe	555.556	17.999	0.9957	530.715
	Cd	500	0.333	0.999	6.322
	Zn	212.766	0.059	0.9955	0.745
	Mn	263.158	0.064	0.9997	1.12
	Cu	46.948	0.013	0.9798	0.083
	Pb	212.766	0.027	0.9995	0.749
	As	90.909	0.027	0.9531	0.204

Adsorption process of removal of each heavy metal by BW are well fitted with Langmuir isotherm as shown in the Table 4.14 above.

4.6.2.4 Roof waste (RW)

Figure 4.31: Isotherm variations of RW samples of Mass optimization

Table 4.10: Isotherm constants of RW samples of Mass optimization

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Langmuir isotherm constants			
		a (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R ²	x/m (mg/g)
RW	Fe	117.647	2.179	0.9715	84.844
	Cd	384.615	0.187	0.9983	2.746
	Zn	208.333	0.058	0.9894	0.717
	Mn	294.118	0.071	0.9991	1.388
	Cu	63.29	0.014	0.9274	0.121
	Pb	312.5	0.04	0.9964	1.626
	As	103.093	0.027	0.9877	0.231

Adsorption process of removal of each heavy metal by RW are well fitted with Langmuir isotherm as shown in the Table 4.15 above.

4.6.2.5 Concrete waste (CW)

Figure 4.32: Isotherm variations of CW samples of Mass optimization

Table 4.11: Isotherm constants of CW samples of Mass optimization

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Langmuir isotherm constants			
		a (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R ²	x/m (mg/g)
CW	Fe	500	10	0.9841	461.15
	Cd	370.37	0.176	0.9936	2.49
	Zn	256.41	0.071	0.9985	1.08
	Mn	370.37	0.122	0.9847	2.993
	Cu	59.172	0.013	0.9824	0.105
	Pb	370.37	0.054	0.9975	2.597
	As	135.135	0.031	0.9921	0.348

Adsorption process of removal of each heavy metal by CW are well fitted with Langmuir isotherm as shown in the Table 4.16 above.

4.6.2 Theoretical adsorption capacities

The theoretical adsorption capacities were obtained from the adsorption isotherm equations for the adsorption isotherm experiment samples. Theoretical adsorption capacity is denoted by x/m and those calculated values are tabulated in the above section. For the calculation of theoretical adsorption capacities of each selected reactive materials, the isotherm constants were used as obtained from the corresponding graphs.

4.7 EFFECT OF INITIAL PH

pH is one of the major parameter controlling the adsorption capacity of metals on to adsorbents. pH affects the solubility of metal ions during the reaction. It also affects the degree of the ionization of adsorbent (Etorki, et al., 2014).

The influence of pH on removal of each heavy metal for each selected reactive materials are described below. They also indicates the pH values where the maximum removal efficiencies were taken place. For all the graphs shown below, the initial pH values were taken for the samples of adsorption isotherm experiments.

4.7.1 Dewatered alum sludge (DAS)

According to the Figure 4.38 shown below maximum removal efficiencies of all heavy metals were occurred at initial pH of 7.49.

Figure 4.33: Effect of initial pH for DAS samples

4.7.2 Floor waste (FW)

As shown in the Figure 4.39 below, maximum removal efficiencies were happened at the initial value of 7.858 for all heavy metals.

Figure 4.34: Effect of initial pH for FW samples

As shown in the Figure 4.40 below, the maximum removal efficiencies of each heavy metals were occurred at an initial pH value of 7.654.

Figure 4.35: Effect of initial pH for BW samples

4.7.4 Roof waste (RW)

As shown in the Figure 4.41 below, the maximum removal efficiencies of each heavy metals were occurred at an initial pH value of 7.81.

Figure 4.36: Effect of initial pH for RW samples

According to the Figure 4.42 shown below maximum removal efficiencies of all heavy metals were occurred at initial pH of 7.49.

Figure 4.37: Effect of initial pH for CW samples

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

Ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate has heavy metals which are very harmful if they are not properly removed. Therefore for the removal of these dissolved heavy metals in the ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate, many researchers have widely used the adsorption processes. In nowadays the need for safe and economical methods for the removal of heavy metals from the ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate became necessitated around the world. Therefore in order to conduct the adsorption process, sorption experiments are conducted by batch technique. Batch experiments are carried out in order to determine the adsorption isotherms of heavy metal ions onto the adsorbents. Since the building wastes are cost effective, readily available and having high adsorbance capacities. Therefore by using these building wastes for the batch sorption experiments will reduce the cost for the process and will give effective results.

Theoretical adsorption capacity values are very important in order to determine the removal of heavy metals by the reactive materials. In this research the theoretical adsorption capacity values were calculated for each heavy metals for each reactive materials of adsorption isotherm experiments. In overall situation, the removal rate of Fe from the ground water contaminated with landfill-leachate samples is very high for each reactive materials, where Brick wastes (BW) has the highest removal efficiency of 530.715 mg/g. The above selected reactive materials also shows high removal rate in removing Pb and Mn. Concrete waste (CW) has high capacity in removing Pb and Mn. The removal rate of Cd is also high by each reactive materials where Brick wastes (BW) shows the highest adsorption capacity of 6.322 mg/g. There is a considerable amount of adsorption of Zn by the reactive materials, where Dewatered alum sludge (DAS) has the maximum adsorption capacity of 1.456 mg/g. The removal rates of heavy metals like Cu and As are very low by each reactive materials comparing to the other heavy metals.

Based on the literature, risk husk and saw dust show a considerable removal efficiency in removing Cd. According to this analysis, brick wastes have a large adsorption capacity of Cd. Fava beans also shows a similar results in removing Pb from the samples. For the removal of Cu from samples coconut husk shows a considerable amount of removing rate where building wastes shows low adsorption capacity of Cu.

Finally it can be concluded that selected building waste material categories such as dewatered alum sludge, floor waste, brick waste, roof waste and concrete waste can effectively be applied as the reactive media in Permeable Reactive Barriers to treat the ground water contaminated by landfill – leachate. Since all these materials are cost effective and readily available in Sri Lanka. Therefore by reusing these materials from construction sites, it will encourage the economic benefits for the users and reduce the problems arising from the waste disposal.

5.2 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended to conduct the batch experiments by varying initial pH and initial adsorbate concentration to find out the variation of the adsorption capacity with those two factors. In addition, there will be a potential for the receipt of different adsorption capacities if the reactive materials are mixed together as adsorbents for batch experiments.

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APPENDIX A

RESULTS OF pH VALUES

Table A.1: pH values of samples of 1st Trial experiment

Sample No	pH
1	8.08
2	7.67
3	6.96
4	7.35
5	7.27
6	6.75
7	6.46

Table A.2: pH values of samples of 2nd Trial experiment

Sample No	pH
1	8.83
2	8.82
3	8.9
4	8.92
5	8.97
Initial	8.13

Table A.3: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –DAS

Sample (g)	pH
Initial	8.59
2.5	8.01
5	7.93
10	7.85
15	7.78
20	7.49

Table A.4: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –FW

Sample (g)	pH
Initial	8.59
2.5	8.2
5	8.18
10	8.03
15	7.89
20	8.17

Table A.5: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –BW

Sample (g)	pH
Initial	8.59
2.5	7.97
5	7.95
7.5	7.9
10	7.71
15	7.67

Table A.6: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –RW

Sample (g)	pH
Initial	8.59
2.5	8.17
5	8.1
10	8.09
12	7.98
15	7.81

Table A.7: pH values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments –CW

Sample (g)	pH
Initial	8.59
2.5	8.03
5	7.96
10	7.82
15	7.89
20	7.7

APPENDIX B

RESULTS OF CONDUCTIVITY VALUES

Table B.1: Conductivity values of samples of 1st Trial experiment

Sample No	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
1	1318
2	871
3	357
4	777
5	431
6	650
7	451

Table B.2: Conductivity values of samples of 2nd Trial experiment

Sample No	Conductivity (mS/cm)
1	8.25
2	8.65
3	8.6
4	8.83
5	8.93
Initial	5.1

Table B.3: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – DAS

Sample (g)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
Initial	2469
2.5	2105
5	1996
10	1914
15	1741
20	1423

Table B.4: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – FW

Sample (g)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
Initial	2469
2.5	1949
5	1475
10	1296
15	1252
20	1178

Table B.5: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – BW

Sample (g)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
Initial	2469
2.5	1741
5	1823
7.5	1801
10	1684
15	1528

Table B.6: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – RW

Sample (g)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
Initial	2469
2.5	2023
5	1845
10	1689
12	1590
15	1552

Table B.7: Conductivity values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – CW

Sample (g)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
Initial	2469
2.5	1785
5	1632
10	1477
15	1402
20	1256

APPENDIX C

RESULTS OF ORP VALUES

Table C.1: ORP values of samples of 1st Trial experiment

Sample No	ORP (mV)
1	195
2	187
3	153
4	171
5	164
6	198
7	155

Table C.2: ORP values of samples of 2nd Trial experiment

Sample No	ORP (mV)
1	173
2	165
3	160
4	153
5	147
Initial	189

Table C.3: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – DAS

Sample (g)	ORP (mV)
Initial	455
2.5	273
5	263
10	236
15	229
20	234

Table C.4: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – FW

Sample (g)	ORP (mV)
Initial	455
2.5	224
5	219
10	215
15	210
20	208

Table C.5: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – BW

Sample (g)	ORP (mV)
Initial	455
2.5	220
5	218
7.5	216
10	213
15	215

Table C.6: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – RW

Sample (g)	ORP (mV)
Initial	455
2.5	222
5	220
10	219
12	219
15	216

Table C.7: ORP values of samples of Adsorption isotherm experiments – CW

Sample (g)	ORP (mV)
Initial	455
2.5	217
5	215
10	216
15	213
20	209

APPENDIX D

RESULTS OF TDS ANALYSIS

Table D.1: TDS analysis for 1st Trial experiment

Sample	Mass of Adsorbent m (mg)	Final TDS C (mg/L)	Final TDS (g)	TDS Removed x (g)	x/m (mg/g)	Log (C)	Log (x/m)	C/(x/m)
1	1000	1140	11.4	37.1	37100	3.06	4.57	0.03
2	5000	680	6.8	41.7	8340	2.83	3.92	0.08
3	10000	6660	66.6	-18.1	-1810	3.82	#NUM!	-3.6
4	20000	1320	13.2	35.3	1765	3.12	3.25	0.75
5	30000	1590	15.9	32.6	1086.6	3.20	3.04	1.46
6	40000	5050	50.5	-2	-50	3.70	#NUM!	-101
7	50000	29200	292	-243.5	-4870	4.47	#NUM!	-6.0

(Initial TDS of influent = 4.85 mg/mL & Volume of sample = 10 mL)

Table D.2: TDS analysis for 2nd Trial experiment

Sample No	Weight of Tile & Cement (g)	Initial Weight of Petri dishes (g)	Weight after oven dried (g)	Remaining Residue (g)
1	2	65.927	65.9592	0.0322
2	4	88.6874	88.7193	0.0319
3	6	84.7869	84.8481	0.0612
4	8	70.3215	70.3464	0.0249
5	10	64.1803	64.2136	0.0333
6	Initial	88.4723	88.5084	0.0361

Mass of Adsorbent m (mg)	Final TDS C (mg/L)	TDS Removed x (g)	x/m (mg/g)	Log (C)	Log (x/m)	C/(x/m)
2000	1073.33	0.0039	1.95	3.03	0.29	550.43
4000	1063.33	0.0042	1.05	3.03	0.02	1012.70
6000	2040.00	-0.0251	-4.18	3.31	#NUM!	-487.65
8000	830.00	0.0112	1.40	2.92	0.15	592.86
10000	1110.00	0.0028	0.28	3.05	-0.55	3964.29

Table D.3: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – DAS

Sample (hrs)	Mass of adsorbent 'm' (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	-	35.0171	35.1167	0.0996	-	-
1	10	35.3252	35.4162	0.091	0.0086	8.63453 8
2	10	34.0681	34.1731	0.105	-0.0054	-5.42169 7.32931
3	10	34.8054	34.8977	0.0923	0.0073	7
4	10	34.8953	35.0001	0.1048	-0.0052	-5.22088 34.5381
6	10	65.9647	66.0299	0.0652	0.0344	5
15	10	64.2749	64.414	0.1391	-0.0395	-39.6586

Table D.4: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – FW

Sample (hrs)	Mass of adsorbent 'm' (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	-	64.2372	64.4512	0.214	-	-
1	10	35.0244	35.2263	0.2019	0.0121	5.65420 6
2	10	34.9105	35.1052	0.1947	0.0193	9.01869 2
3	10	34.0899	34.2854	0.1955	0.0185	8.64486 11.5420
4	10	34.4128	34.6021	0.1893	0.0247	6
6	10	34.8154	35.0005	0.1851	0.0289	13.5046 7
12	10	35.3495	35.5316	0.1821	0.0319	14.9065 4

Table D.5: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – BW

Sample (hrs)	Mass of adsorbent 'm' (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	-	70.4164	70.4851	0.0687	-	-
1	10	35.0044	35.0685	0.0641	0.0046	6.695779
2	10	35.318	35.3773	0.0593	0.0094	13.68268
3	10	34.7883	34.8425	0.0542	0.0145	21.10626
4	10	34.9061	34.9554	0.0493	0.0194	28.23872
6	10	34.4002	34.4512	0.051	0.0177	25.76419
12	10	34.0511	34.0941	0.043	0.0257	37.40902

Table D.6: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – RW

Sample (hrs)	Mass of adsorbent 'm' (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	-	85.0472	85.1164	0.0692	-	-
1	10	35.4636	35.4886	0.025	0.0442	63.87283
2	10	34.4066	34.4666	0.06	0.0092	13.2948
3	10	35.022	35.0663	0.0443	0.0249	35.98266
4	10	34.8069	34.8621	0.0552	0.014	20.23121
6	10	34.204	34.215	0.011	0.0582	84.10405
12	10	34.9446	34.9721	0.0275	0.0417	60.26012

Table D.7: TDS analysis of kinematic experiments – CW

Sample (hrs)	Mass of adsorbent 'm' (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	-	70.3898	70.5058	0.116	-	-
1	10	35.3317	35.4405	0.1088	0.0072	6.206897
2	10	34.0544	34.1652	0.1108	0.0052	4.482759
3	10	34.7974	34.9122	0.1148	0.0012	1.034483
4	10	35.0166	35.1238	0.1072	0.0088	7.586207
6	10	34.8934	34.9013	0.0079	0.1081	93.18966
12	10	34.403	34.5142	0.1112	0.0048	4.137931

Table D.8: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – DAS

Sample (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	34.4026	34.4874	0.0848	-	-
2.5	34.8	34.8574	0.0574	0.0274	32.31132
5	34.9027	34.9564	0.0537	0.0311	36.67453
10	35.3441	35.4103	0.0662	0.0186	21.93396
15	35.026	35.1066	0.0806	0.0042	4.95283
20	34.0656	34.1428	0.0772	0.0076	8.962264

Table D.9: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – FW

Sample (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	91.0453	91.1632	0.1179	-	-
2.5	65.9731	66.0058	0.0327	0.0852	72.26463
5	66.0235	66.0553	0.0318	0.0861	73.02799
10	88.8203	88.8558	0.0355	0.0824	69.88974
15	90.1812	90.2294	0.0482	0.0697	59.1179
20	88.6484	88.682	0.0336	0.0843	71.50127

Table D.10: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – BW

Sample (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	66.0574	66.1254	0.068	-	-
2.5	66.0196	66.025	0.0054	0.0626	92.05882
5	66.0431	66.0644	0.0213	0.0467	68.67647
7.5	90.2018	90.2314	0.0296	0.0384	56.47059
10	88.853	88.8849	0.0319	0.0361	53.08824
15	88.6676	88.6888	0.0212	0.0468	68.82353

Table D.11: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – RW

Sample (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	65.2354	65.331	0.0956	-	-
2.5	64.3034	64.3583	0.0549	0.0407	42.57322
5	66.0475	66.056	0.0085	0.0871	91.10879
10	66.0451	66.0874	0.0423	0.0533	55.75314
12	90.1985	90.2454	0.0469	0.0487	50.94142
15	88.6682	88.7127	0.0445	0.0511	53.45188

Table D.12: TDS analysis of adsorption isotherm experiments – CW

Sample (g)	Weight of empty petri dish (g)	Weight of residue + petri dish (g)	Weight of dissolved solids (g)	TDS removed 'x' (g)	x/m
Initial	35.2145	35.2896	0.0751	-	-
2.5	35.3525	35.4029	0.0504	0.0247	32.88948
5	35.0359	35.0844	0.0485	0.0266	35.41944
10	34.1144	34.1689	0.0545	0.0206	27.43009
15	34.4667	34.5359	0.0692	0.0059	7.856192
20	34.8055	34.8656	0.0601	0.015	19.97337

APPENDIX E

HEAVY METALS REMOVAL OF KINEMATIC EXPERIMENTS

Table E.1: Fe removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.147	0.775	-	-
1	0.141	0.744	0.031	3.989
2	0.128	0.677	0.098	12.633
3	0.093	0.497	0.278	35.904
4	0.105	0.558	0.216	27.926
6	0.084	0.450	0.325	41.888
15	0.097	0.517	0.258	33.245

Table E.2: Cd removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	19.562	-	-
1	13.366	6.196	31.674
2	8.039	11.523	58.905
3	6.059	13.503	69.027
4	6.999	12.563	64.221
6	5.744	13.818	70.637
15	6.194	13.368	68.337

Table E.3: Zn removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	26.575	-	-
1	21.55	5.025	18.909
2	19.512	7.063	26.578
3	20.635	5.94	22.352
4	16.542	10.033	37.754
6	14.753	11.822	44.485
15	15.78	10.795	40.621

Table E.4: Mn removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	36.319	-	-
1	25.963	10.356	28.514
2	22.742	13.577	37.383
3	26.725	9.594	26.416
4	21.414	14.905	41.039
6	18.178	18.141	49.949
15	17.224	19.095	52.576

Table E.5: Cu removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	130.013	-	-
1	95.632	34.381	26.444
2	81.212	48.801	37.535
3	86.241	43.772	33.667
4	73.532	56.481	43.443
6	78.108	51.905	39.923
15	75.675	54.338	41.794

Table E.6: Pb removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	76.494	-	-
1	46.251	30.243	39.536
2	42.847	33.647	43.986
3	34.446	42.048	54.969
4	18.308	58.186	76.066
6	17.935	58.559	76.554
15	18.014	58.48	76.450

Table E.7: As removal by DAS of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	67.887	-	-
1	56.411	11.476	16.905
2	47.468	20.419	30.078
3	45.608	22.279	32.818
4	46.812	21.075	31.044
6	45.024	22.863	33.678
15	43.711	24.176	35.612

Table E.8: Fe removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.135	0.713034518	-	-
1	0.094	0.48428645	0.228748068	32.08092486
2	0.115	0.592478104	0.120556414	16.90751445
3	0.065	0.334878928	0.37815559	53.03468208
4	0.046	0.236991242	0.476043277	66.76300578
6	0.075	0.386398764	0.326635755	45.80924855
12	0.068	0.350334879	0.362699639	50.86705202

Table E.9: Cd removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	13.818	-	-
1	6.296	7.522	54.436
2	2.406	11.412	82.588
3	0.825	12.993	94.030
4	1.282	12.536	90.722
6	0.274	13.544	98.017
12	0.237	13.581	98.285

Table E.10: Zn removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	26.575	-	-
1	17.317	9.258	34.837
2	16.602	9.973	37.528
3	16.691	9.884	37.193
4	16.014	10.561	39.740
6	15.776	10.799	40.636
12	15.022	11.553	43.473

Table E.11: Mn removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	36.319	-	-
1	21.697	14.622	40.260
2	20.156	16.163	44.503
3	14.305	22.014	60.613
4	12.767	23.552	64.848
6	18.324	17.995	49.547
12	11.926	24.393	67.163

Table E.12: Cu removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	130.013	-	-
1	99.311	30.702	23.615
2	90.961	39.052	30.037
3	80.428	49.585	38.138
4	80.556	49.457	38.040
6	80.446	49.567	38.125
12	80.498	49.515	38.085

Table E.13: Pb removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	76.494	-	-
1	38.014	38.48	50.305
2	34.201	42.293	55.289
3	25.302	51.192	66.923
4	17.931	58.563	76.559
6	18.168	58.326	76.249
12	16.759	59.735	78.091

Table E.14: As removal by FW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	67.887	-	-
1	54.873	13.014	19.170
2	44.349	23.538	34.672
3	41.749	26.138	38.502
4	39.904	27.983	41.220
6	36.922	30.965	45.613
12	36.923	30.964	45.611

Table E.15: Fe removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.114	0.605	-	-
1	0.104	0.536	0.069	11.414
2	0.061	0.314	0.291	48.041
3	0.037	0.191	0.414	68.484
4	0.028	0.144	0.461	76.150
6	0.026	0.134	0.471	77.853
12	0.024	0.124	0.481	79.557

Table E.16: Cd removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	13.818	-	-
1	8.439	5.379	38.927
2	7.739	6.079	43.993
3	7.563	6.255	45.267
4	7.256	6.562	47.489
6	6.834	6.984	50.543
12	6.739	7.079	51.230

Table E.17: Zn removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	26.575	-	-
1	19.479	7.096	26.702
2	19.318	7.257	27.308
3	16.635	9.94	37.404
4	17.5	9.075	34.149
6	16.212	10.363	38.995
12	16.595	9.98	37.554

Table E.18: Mn removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	36.319	-	-
1	31.485	4.834	13.310
2	24.595	11.724	32.281
3	26.238	10.081	27.757
4	17.095	19.224	52.931
6	20.544	15.775	43.435
12	18.084	18.235	50.208

Table E.19: Cu removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	130.013	-	-
1	80.708	49.305	37.923
2	80.639	49.374	37.976
3	80.461	49.552	38.113
4	80.619	49.394	37.992
6	80.518	49.495	38.069
12	80.476	49.537	38.102

Table E.20: Pb removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	76.494	-	-
1	51.263	25.231	32.984
2	46.544	29.95	39.153
3	39.412	37.082	48.477
4	31.946	44.548	58.237
6	16.732	59.762	78.126
12	16.72	59.774	78.142

Table E.21: As removal by BW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	67.887	-	-
1	43.235	24.652	36.313
2	40.401	27.486	40.488
3	41.211	26.676	39.295
4	42.252	25.635	37.761
6	39.701	28.186	41.519
12	39.358	28.529	42.024

Table E.22: Fe removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.114	0.605	-	-
1	0.108	0.574	0.031	5.111
2	0.106	0.564	0.041	6.814
3	0.101	0.538	0.067	11.073
4	0.089	0.476	0.129	21.295
6	0.096	0.512	0.093	15.332
12	0.093	0.497	0.108	17.888

Table E.23: Cd removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	19.562	-	-
1	17.021	2.541	12.989
2	15.327	4.235	21.649
3	14.946	4.616	23.597
4	13.583	5.979	30.564
6	13.485	6.077	31.065
12	11.365	8.197	41.903

Table E.24: Zn removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	26.575	-	-
1	17.572	9.003	33.878
2	17.065	9.51	35.786
3	15.805	10.77	40.527
4	16.245	10.33	38.871
6	15.021	11.554	43.477
12	15.027	11.548	43.454

Table E.25: Mn removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	36.319	-	-
1	25.871	10.448	28.767
2	18.838	17.481	48.132
3	18.785	17.534	48.278
4	20.241	16.078	44.269
6	19.874	16.445	45.279
12	18.424	17.895	49.272

Table E.26: Cu removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	130.013	-	-
1	108.821	21.192	16.300
2	80.622	49.391	37.989
3	80.508	49.505	38.077
4	80.52	49.493	38.068
6	80.334	49.679	38.211
12	80.527	49.486	38.062

Table E.27: Pb removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	76.494	-	-
1	68.179	8.315	10.870
2	59.607	16.887	22.076
3	58.397	18.097	23.658
4	60.007	16.487	21.553
6	53.377	23.117	30.221
12	50.893	25.601	33.468

Table E.28: As removal by RW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	67.887	-	-
1	54.004	13.883	20.450
2	53.782	14.105	20.777
3	47.117	20.77	30.595
4	48.773	19.114	28.156
6	34.706	33.181	48.877
12	23.658	44.229	65.151

Table E.29: Fe removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.114	0.605	-	-
1	0.072	0.388	0.216	35.775
2	0.062	0.337	0.268	44.293
3	0.043	0.239	0.366	60.477
4	0.06	0.327	0.278	45.997
6	0.058	0.316	0.289	47.700
12	0.041	0.229	0.376	62.181

Table E.30: Cd removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	19.562	-	-
1	19.012	0.55	2.812
2	17.791	1.771	9.053
3	16.451	3.111	15.903
4	12.099	7.463	38.150
6	9.954	9.608	49.116
12	8.164	11.398	58.266

Table E.31: Zn removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	26.575	-	-
1	17.349	9.226	34.717
2	16.803	9.772	36.771
3	15.747	10.828	40.745
4	15.634	10.941	41.170
6	15.143	11.432	43.018
12	15.027	11.548	43.454

Table E.32: Mn removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	36.319	-	-
1	25.041	11.278	31.053
2	21.594	14.725	40.544
3	20.617	15.702	43.234
4	18.516	17.803	49.018
6	16.465	19.854	54.666
12	16.971	19.348	53.272

Table E.33: Cu removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	130.013	-	-
1	114.954	15.059	11.583
2	112.571	17.442	13.416
3	100.559	29.454	22.655
4	80.668	49.345	37.954
6	80.509	49.504	38.076
12	80.447	49.566	38.124

Table E.34: Pb removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	76.494	-	-
1	63.753	12.741	16.656
2	59.409	17.085	22.335
3	59.912	16.582	21.678
4	47.917	28.577	37.358
6	18.827	57.667	75.388
12	17.069	59.425	77.686

Table E.35: As removal by CW of kinematic experiments

Sample (hrs)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	67.887	-	-
1	67.489	0.398	0.586
2	55.109	12.778	18.822
3	49.244	18.643	27.462
4	37.305	30.582	45.048
6	33.036	34.851	51.337
12	35.035	32.852	48.392

APPENDIX F

HEAVY METALS REMOVAL OF ADSORPTION ISOTHERM EXPERIMENTS

Table F.1: Fe removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.227	1.187	-	-
2.5	0.2	1.048	0.139	11.719
5	0.182	0.955	0.232	19.531
10	0.142	0.749	0.438	36.892
15	0.156	0.821	0.366	30.816
20	0.141	0.744	0.443	37.326

Table F.2: Cd removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	38.454	-	-
2.5	16.648	21.806	56.707
5	12.467	25.987	67.579
10	12.43	26.024	67.676
15	12.556	25.898	67.348
20	12.397	26.057	67.761

Table F.3: Zn removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	59.558	-	-
2.5	35.08	24.478	41.099
5	29.175	30.383	51.014
10	28.175	31.383	52.693
15	21.325	38.233	64.195
20	18.829	40.729	68.385

Table F.4: Mn removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	66.772	-	-
2.5	35.852	30.92	46.307
5	34.928	31.844	47.691
10	33.414	33.358	49.958
15	33.71	33.062	49.515
20	32.96	33.812	50.638

Table F.5: Cu removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	136.542	-	-
2.5	111.615	24.927	18.256
5	86.557	49.985	36.608
10	86.499	50.043	36.650
15	82.301	54.241	39.725
20	82.394	54.148	39.657

Table F.6: Pb removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	130.772	-	-
2.5	63.564	67.208	51.393
5	42.172	88.6	67.752
10	41.716	89.056	68.100
15	41.201	89.571	68.494
20	40.028	90.744	69.391

Table F.7: As removal by DAS of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	83.241	-	-
2.5	66.518	16.723	20.090
5	60.187	23.054	27.695
10	61.941	21.3	25.588
15	52.735	30.506	36.648
20	51.559	31.682	38.061

Table F.8: Fe removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.227	1.187	-	-
2.5	0.186	0.958	0.229	19.271
5	0.161	0.829	0.358	30.122
10	0.125	0.644	0.543	45.747
15	0.119	0.613	0.574	48.351
20	0.111	0.572	0.615	51.823

Table F.9: Cd removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	38.454	-	-
2.5	16.572	21.882	56.904
5	14.425	24.029	62.488
10	12.479	25.975	67.548
15	12.489	25.965	67.522
20	12.355	26.099	67.871

Table F.10: Zn removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	59.558	-	-
2.5	37.836	21.722	36.472
5	35.145	24.413	40.990
10	29.403	30.155	50.631
15	28.176	31.382	52.691
20	29.314	30.244	50.781

Table F.11: Mn removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	66.772	-	-
2.5	34.343	32.429	48.567
5	33.904	32.868	49.224
10	33.205	33.567	50.271
15	31.857	34.915	52.290
20	32.056	34.716	51.992

Table F.12: Cu removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	136.542	-	-
2.5	122.485	14.057	10.295
5	109.225	27.317	20.006
10	107.018	29.524	21.623
15	99.419	37.123	27.188
20	98.471	38.071	27.882

Table F.13: Pb removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	130.722	-	-
2.5	69.176	61.546	47.082
5	48.652	82.07	62.782
10	48.089	82.633	63.213
15	47.266	83.456	63.842
20	45.632	85.09	65.092

Table F.14: As removal by FW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	83.241	-	-
2.5	65.954	17.287	20.767
5	64.182	19.059	22.896
10	63.433	19.808	23.796
15	50.002	33.239	39.931
20	47.143	36.098	43.366

Table F.15: Fe removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.227	1.187	-	-
2.5	0.089	0.459	0.728	61.372
5	0.036	0.185	1.002	84.375
7.5	0.034	0.175	1.012	85.243
10	0.031	0.160	1.027	86.545
15	0.021	0.108	1.079	90.885

Table F.16: Cd removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	38.454	-	-
2.5	12.421	26.033	67.699
5	10.411	28.043	72.926
7.5	10.479	27.975	72.749
10	9.489	28.965	75.324
15	9.4	29.054	75.555

Table F.17: Zn removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	59.558	-	-
2.5	37.113	22.445	37.686
5	35.603	23.955	40.221
7.5	34.93	24.628	41.351
10	28.112	31.446	52.799
15	26.853	32.705	54.913

Table F.18: Mn removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	66.772	-	-
2.5	33.529	33.243	49.786
5	32.932	33.84	50.680
7.5	32.066	34.706	51.977
10	31.367	35.405	53.024
15	31.785	34.987	52.398

Table F.19: Cu removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	136.542	-	-
2.5	116.94	19.602	14.356
5	98.669	37.873	27.737
7.5	94.076	42.466	31.101
10	92.398	44.144	32.330
15	90.623	45.919	33.630

Table F.20: Pb removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	130.722	-	-
2.5	72.346	58.376	44.657
5	71.299	59.423	45.458
7.5	69.416	61.306	46.898
10	69.574	61.148	46.777
15	67.841	62.881	48.103

Table F.21: As removal by BW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	83.241	-	-
2.5	66.952	16.289	19.568
5	52.476	30.765	36.959
7.5	47.929	35.312	42.421
10	50.602	32.639	39.210
15	42.779	40.462	48.608

Table F.22: Fe removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.227	1.187	-	-
2.5	0.175	0.919	0.268	22.569
5	0.158	0.832	0.355	29.948
10	0.122	0.646	0.541	45.573
12	0.112	0.595	0.592	49.913
15	0.114	0.605	0.582	49.045

Table F.23: Cd removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	38.454	-	-
2.5	17.418	21.036	54.704
5	16.421	22.033	57.297
10	12.489	25.965	67.522
12	12.408	26.046	67.733
15	11.443	27.011	70.242

Table F.24: Zn removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	59.558	-	-
2.5	36.409	23.149	38.868
5	33.721	25.837	43.381
10	30.479	29.079	48.825
12	30.766	28.792	48.343
15	27.388	32.17	54.015

Table F.25: Mn removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	66.772	-	-
2.5	32.542	34.23	51.264
5	30.464	36.308	54.376
10	29.254	37.518	56.188
12	29.005	37.767	56.561
15	28.412	38.36	57.449

Table F.26: Cu removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	136.542	-	-
2.5	115.236	21.306	15.604
5	102.54	34.002	24.902
10	98.623	37.919	27.771
12	85.325	51.217	37.510
15	84.514	52.028	38.104

Table F.27: Pb removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	130.722	-	-
2.5	65.235	65.487	50.096
5	58.412	72.31	55.316
10	54.284	76.438	58.474
12	50.541	80.181	61.337
15	49.774	80.948	61.924

Table F.28: As removal by RW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	83.241	-	-
2.5	62.122	21.119	25.371
5	61.329	21.912	26.324
10	59.009	24.232	29.111
12	53.311	29.93	35.956
15	49.251	33.99	40.833

Table F.29: Fe removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Absorbance (A)	Concentration (mg/L)	Fe removed (mg/L)	Fe removed %
Initial	0.227	1.187	-	-
2.5	0.1	0.533	0.654	55.122
5	0.072	0.388	0.799	67.274
10	0.04	0.224	0.963	81.163
15	0.034	0.193	0.994	83.767
20	0.02	0.121	1.066	89.844

Table F.30: Cd removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd removed %
Initial	38.454	-	-
2.5	18.172	20.282	52.744
5	15.402	23.052	59.947
10	13.372	25.082	65.226
15	12.503	25.951	67.486
20	11.433	27.021	70.268

Table F.31: Zn removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Zn removed %
Initial	59.558	-	-
2.5	31.63	27.928	46.892
5	30.944	28.614	48.044
10	31.028	28.53	47.903
15	26.944	32.614	54.760
20	29.749	29.809	50.050

Table F.32: Mn removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mn removed %
Initial	66.772	-	-
2.5	35.304	31.468	47.128
5	25.529	41.243	61.767
10	17.098	49.674	74.393
15	15.338	51.434	77.029
20	14.586	52.186	78.156

Table F.33: Cu removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cu removed %
Initial	136.542	-	-
2.5	112.17	24.372	17.849
5	110.235	26.307	19.267
10	103.235	33.307	24.393
15	93.541	43.001	31.493
20	92.471	44.071	32.277

Table F.34: Pb removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Pb removed %
Initial	130.722	-	-
2.5	58.632	72.09	55.148
5	48.506	82.216	62.894
10	42.632	88.09	67.387
15	41.235	89.487	68.456
20	42.574	88.148	67.432

Table F.35: As removal by CW of adsorption isotherm experiments

Adsorbent (g)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	As removed %
Initial	83.241	-	-
2.5	57.923	25.318	30.415
5	49.284	33.957	40.794
10	48.545	34.696	41.681
15	45.985	37.256	44.757
20	45.632	37.609	45.181

APPENDIX G

SUMMARY TABLES

Table G.1: Time optimization experiment results

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Removal efficiency %	Optimum Time (hrs)
DAS	Fe	41.89	6
	Cd	70.64	6
	Zn	44.49	6
	Mn	52.58	6
	Cu	43.44	6
	Pb	76.55	6
	As	35.61	6
FW	Fe	66.76	6
	Cd	98.28	6
	Zn	43.47	6
	Mn	67.16	4
	Cu	38.12	6
	Pb	78.09	6
	As	45.61	6
BW	Fe	79.56	6
	Cd	51.23	6
	Zn	39	6
	Mn	52.93	6
	Cu	38.1	3
	Pb	78.14	6
	As	42.02	6
RW	Fe	19.8	6
	Cd	40.05	6
	Zn	43.47	6
	Mn	49.27	6
	Cu	38.21	4
	Pb	33.47	6
	As	65.15	12
CW	Fe	62.18	6
	Cd	58.27	12
	Zn	43.45	6
	Mn	54.67	6
	Cu	38.12	6
	Pb	77.69	6
	As	51.34	6

Table G.2: Mass optimization experiment results

Reactive Material	Heavy metal	Removal efficiency %	Optimum Mass (g)
DAS	Fe	37.33	10
	Cd	67.68	10
	Zn	68.38	20
	Mn	50.64	15
	Cu	39.72	10
	Pb	69.39	15
	As	38.06	15
FW	Fe	51.82	15
	Cd	67.84	15
	Zn	52.69	15
	Mn	52.29	15
	Cu	27.88	15
	Pb	65.09	10
	As	43.37	20
BW	Fe	90.89	10
	Cd	75.56	10
	Zn	54.91	15
	Mn	53.02	10
	Cu	33.62	10
	Pb	48.1	15
	As	48.6	15
RW	Fe	49.91	12
	Cd	70.24	15
	Zn	54.01	15
	Mn	57.45	12
	Cu	37.1	12
	Pb	61.92	12
	As	40.83	15
CW	Fe	89.84	15
	Cd	70.27	15
	Zn	54.76	15
	Mn	78.15	15
	Cu	32.28	15
	Pb	68.46	15
	As	45.18	15